

Structural Equation Model of Job Performance among Restaurant Employees in Davao Region

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Abstract: The purpose of this quantitative research was to determine the best fit model involving the following exogenous variables: employee engagement, entrepreneurial marketing and employee empowerment in relation to endogenous variable job performance of restaurant employees. For the purpose of data collection, a survey questionnaire was administered to 403 restaurant employees in Davao Region. Structural equation modelling was used to find the best fit model. The results show that employee engagement, entrepreneurial marketing and employee empowerment show significant relationship with employee's job performance. However, among the three identified exogenous variables there were other variables that shows interrelationship emerged as key predictors of employee's job performance as depicted in the final and best fit model of this study.

Keywords: employee engagement, entrepreneurial marketing, employee empowerment, SEM, Philippines

I. Introduction

1.1 Rationale

Restaurants, cafeterias, refreshment places, fast food places and drinking establishments that under food service industry have been met with poor performance of the employees (Ukandu & Ukpere, 2013). One of the biggest problems the food service industry has faced is a lack of skills (Dunning, Bloom & Creamer, 2015). Managers often consider that performing a duty publicly despite having inadequate skills adversely affects the efficiency of their service and can demean and discredit workers for their poor performance (Adnan, Rahman, & Ahmad, 2018). Without properly trained and motivated workers, commonly companies cannot have a high volume of performance. Knowingly, a restaurant job is a publicly performed job which means that the services given to their customers pose inadequate skills at risk (Ukandu & Ukpere, 2014).

Job Performance is a broad multidimensional framework aimed at achieving outcomes and has a strong link to an organization's strategic goals (Obicci, 2015). The total expected value for the organization of the discrete behavioral episodes a person experiences over a standard duration is specified (Gondal & Husain, 2013). Employee efficiency is critical for providing the restaurants with quality services, which in turn raises customer satisfaction (Karatepe, 2013). Management must understand the importance of employee performance, and take steps to cultivate and empower employees to perform well. When an organization's job performance is efficient, it can take the lead in the industry and capture the opportunities on the market (Chei, Yee, Men & Bee, 2014).

Employee engagement greatly increases any organisation's overall performance (Saradha & Patrick, 2011). This greatly impacts retention of staff, efficiency, engagement, customer satisfaction, business credibility and overall value of stakeholders (Sundaray, 2011). On the other hand, small independent restaurant businesses have identified entrepreneurial marketing as a method (Jogarathnam, 2002). Entrepreneurial and market orientation are attributed a positive impact on firm performance (Long, 2013). Employee empowerment is a motivational tool intended to improve efficiency if properly managed by increased levels of employee engagement and self-determination (Meyerson & Dewettinck, 2012). This therefore contributes to the profitability of the company, customer satisfaction and better profits (Dobre 2013).

Cognizant of the significance of employee job performance, extensive research on this subject has been carried out on possible variables that may be correlated with it. It has been found that the variables are significant in terms of: employee engagement (Karavardar, 2014), entrepreneurial marketing (Jogarathnam, 2017; Umeze & Ohen, 2015) and employee empowerment (Kim, Losekoot & Milne, 2013) are to be related to job performance. As Crant (2000) has defined motivation to be positive in the sense that motivation is important in coping with high-performing workers, otherwise their performance will be deteriorating or they will simply leave the job. On the previous context the researcher has chosen to conduct this analysis in the pursuit of developing the best fit model that can explain the job performance of an employee between service restaurants. The outcome of this research can be a basis for the design of the operating programs and policies of suitable restaurants. The outcome of this study would also be of great interest to restaurateurs, scholars, entrepreneurs and researchers, as it can have important applications for an increasing body of

knowledge and contribute to the literature of business. Having this undertaking would therefore be a matter of social significance too.

1.2 Research Objective

The research aimed to determine the best fit model of job performance among restaurant employees in the Davao Region as influenced by employee engagement, entrepreneurial marketing and empowerment of workers. The study specifically dealt with the following objectives:

- To determine the degree of employee engagement of restaurant

Employees in terms of:

- emotional engagement;
- rational identification;
- compatibility;
- team orientation; and
- Motivation.

- To measure the level of entrepreneurial marketing of restaurant

Employees in terms of :

- proactive orientation;
- opportunity driven;
- customer-intensity
- innovation-focused
- risk management; and
- Value creation.

- To estimate the level of employee empowerment of restaurant employees in terms of:

- meaningfulness;
- competences;
- self-determination; and
- Impacts.

- To evaluate the level of job performance of restaurant employees in terms of:

- stress;
- working environment;
- workload; and
- Salary.

- To test the relationship between:

- employee engagement and job performance;
- entrepreneurial marketing and job performance;
- Employee empowerment and job performance.

- To determine the best fit model for job performance among restaurant employees in Davao Region.

1.3 Hypothesis

The following null hypotheses were tested with a significance level of 0.05:

- ✚ There is no significant correlation between:

- employee engagement and job performance;
- entrepreneurial marketing and job performance; and
- Employee empowerment and job performance.

- ✚ There is no model that best fits job performance among restaurant employees in Davao Region.

1.4 Review of Related Literature

This segment includes the analysis of related literature and studies in international and local settings that led significantly to this study's conceptualization. The following are empirical reviews of related studies. The following literature review begins with an extensive analysis highlighting the effects of employee engagement (Kirsch, 2016) using the following indicators: emotional engagement, rational identification compatibility team orientation and motivation; entrepreneurial marketing (Fiore, Niehm, Son & Sadachar, 2013); with the following indicators: *proactive orientation, opportunity driven, customer-intensity, innovation-focused, risk management and value creation*; employee empowerment (Ugboro, 2006) with the following indicators: *meaningfulness, competence, self-determination and impact*; to employee job performance (Munisamy, 2013) among service restaurants with the following indicators: *stress, working environment, workload and salary*.

Employee Engagement

Employee engagement is based on trust, honesty, bidirectional dedication and cooperation between an organization and its members. Crawford, Rich, Buckman and Bergeron (2014) describe employee engagement as a workplace approach that provides the right work conditions for all members of an organization to do their best every

day, committed to the goals and values of their organization; motivated to contribute to organizational success, with an enhanced sense of their own well-being. It is an approach that increases the chances of business success and leads to efficiency, profitability and well-being of the company and the employee. It fluctuates from low to high. It can be nurtured, measured and increased dramatically; it can fail and throw away. In addition, this also reduces employee turn-over, absenteeism and organizational conflicts (Jones, Ni & Wilson, 2009; Mortimer, 2010).

Previous studies reveal that employee engagement has a significant influence on employee performance (Bagyo 2013). Therefore, a dedicated employee is well aware of the business climate and strives to enhance efficiency inside the job with the help of other employees for the benefits of the company Mani (2011). In addition, committed employees put all their energy and passion into their jobs and care about the organization's future (Mani, 2011; Sundaray, 2011).

Employee engagement is a fundamental concept when it comes to trying to explain the essence of an organization's relationship with its workers, both qualitatively and quantitatively (Anitha, 2014). Engaged employee is described as one who is fully absorbed and enthusiastic about his/her job and therefore takes proactive steps to further the company's reputation and interests (Breevaart, Bakker, Hetland, Demerouti, Olsen & Espevik, 2014). A dedicated employee has a positive attitude toward the company and its values.

Employee engagement understands one's position in an organization as defined by Mone and London (2014), and being sighted and energized about where it fits in with the mission and goals of the organization. It's also about having a clear view of how a company achieves its mission and objectives, how it adjusts to help achieve those goals and having an opinion in his undertaking to give suggestions and express views that are taken into consideration when decisions are taken. Engaged employee is about being actively comprised as a team member, working on clear goals, being optimistic and motivated, receiving regular and positive input, being assisted in the development of new skills, being praised and appreciated for achievement.

Consequently, according to Saks and Gruman (2014), an company with a high degree of employee engagement could be expected to outperform those with low employee commitment. Engagement of workers first emerged in the 1990s as a term in management theory, becoming common in management practice in the 2000s, but it remains disputed. It is in an undefined relationship to earlier construct such as morality and job satisfaction. Notwithstanding academic criticism, employee-engagement approaches are well established in human resource management and internal communications. In addition, Mishra, Boynton and Mishra (2014) said committed organizations have strong and sincere values, with clear proof of confidence and fairness based on mutual respect, understanding and upholding two-way agreements and responsibilities between employers and employees. This concerns positive attitudes and behaviors which lead to better business results, it is also about workers having pride and loyalty working for the company, being an organization's great advocate for clients, workforces and consumers, going the extra mile to finish the job.

According to Anthony-McMann, Ellinger, Astakhova and Halbesleben (2017), the meanings of engagement differ in the weight that they offer to the person vs. the organization in establishing commitment. Recent experience has put commitment drivers across this continuum, within the individual employee's psyche for example, promising recruiting systems, which filtered out 'disengaged' job applicants to focus mainly on the actions and expenditures that the company makes in promoting involvement. These definitional issues for practitioners are potentially serious. Estimates from different sources are not easily comparable with specific (and often proprietary) interpretations of the object being measured. Engagement work remains open to the challenge that its basic assumptions, as Keenoy (2013) describes them, are 'normative' and 'aspirational' rather than empirical or operational-and thus risk being perceived as the language of 'motherhood and apple pie' by other organizational participants.

Many have often viewed employee engagement as an indication of a competitive advantage (Menguc, Auh, Fisher & Haddad, 2013). However, Truss, Shantz, Soane, Alfes and Delbridge (2013), argued that employee engagement cannot be accomplished through a mechanistic strategy that seeks to extract discretionary effort by manipulating the attention and emotions of employees. Employees see very easily through such efforts, and may become cynical and disillusioned. One measure of employee engagement is emotional engagement. Emotional engagement includes curiosity, frustration, joy, anxiety and other affective states, any of which can affect the participation of learners or their ongoing efforts (Anthony, McMann, Ellinger, Astakhova & Halbesleben, 2017). The ability to engage with an individual or group emotionally is an important factor in the development of a constructive and helpful relationship. Whether an event is viewed as positive or negative, regardless of the outcome, often the difference is. Shuck and Reio Jr. (2014) proposed that participation should be a necessary course of action taken by practitioners in conflict resolution in the process of mediation, coaching, or counseling.

Emotional engagement often stems from the sense that the work done is important, and that the workers are dedicated, enthusiastic and inspired by their work and the purpose of the organization (Schutte & Loi, 2014). In the end, a more committed, happy workforce leads to growth in the business. However, Schaufeli and Salanova (2014) noted that companies frequently concentrate all their energy on where individuals fall on the engagement scale at the risk of losing sight of where they are as a company. Combined with an individual emphasis on employee engagement, Shuck, Ghosh, Zigarmi and Nimon (2013) indicated that organizations should also follow a business engagement perspective that allows them to quickly assess where the organization falls on a specific level of engagement, and make the necessary changes to enhance their overall employee engagement strategy. Commitment to employee participation strengthens the corporate culture, and often leads to higher job satisfaction and retention rates. Emotional engagement created meaningful connections that cut through the workplace's hectic routine while setting up the company as a whole to achieve great success.

Rational recognition is also an indicator of employee engagement. Rational (thinking) commitment is the degree to which workers feel that their own interests are taken into account by their supervisors, teams or organisations, whether they are political, developmental or technical. Rational commitment has also been described as the degree to which employees feel that someone or something within their organizations is providing financial, developmental, or professional benefits in their best interest (Chernyak-Hai & Tziner, 2016). Employees can be loyal to the company because it satisfies a logical and rational need to provide a means of financial stability. An employee may also be dedicated to a job because it meets a career goal or professional needs-related long-term purpose.

Further, Shuck et al.(2017) identified rational commitment to the understanding of employees' roles and responsibilities (the "thinking" part of the equation). Orletsky (2015) gave another concept that rational commitment is what a person agrees to give to the company when hired; his time and effort for financial compensation, personal growth and the chance to achieve his career aspirations. It is also the desire of an employee to go "above and beyond" calling for duties, such as helping those with heavy workloads, volunteering for extra tasks and finding ways to perform their jobs more efficiently. Strom, Sears and Kelly (2014) said fair engagement requires understanding of how people benefit from their individual and departmental contributions to the enterprise at large. Workers with a strong moral commitment are more likely to invest discretionary time in their work than others.

Compatibility also provides a measure of employee engagement. The continuity of the manager partnership (executive, manager, boss, and team leader) and employee impacts dramatically on the performance of workers (Arezes, Dinis-Carvalho & Alves, 2015). Managers and employees who respect the style of each other are highly engaged and productive. Nevertheless, Basha and Maiti (2017) pointed out that managers "out of step" with their employees frequently cause low productivity, declining morale, and high unnecessary turnover of employees. The employee's partnership with their employer is a significant factor behind employee engagement and productivity. Research shows repeatedly that employees leave an organization mainly because of disagreement with their boss (Qian, Shi & Zhou 2015). The more an employee knows a boss, the more effective they can be.

In addition, in order to achieve defined targets, workers must be able to effectively communicate information among them, as Cullen, Edwards, Casper, and Gue (2014) affirm. The technology comparison, where two people do not share similar language or reference point, breaks down the connection resulting in information loss and ultimately decreased efficiency. The recruiting of compatibility begins with the development of a healthy corporate culture that attracts compatible high-performance talent and develops processes to sustain and improve those talents (McCann, Sparks & Kohntopp, 2017).

Team-orientation is another measure of employee engagement. According to Guillaume, Dawson, Otake, Ebede, Woods and West (2017), organizations emphasizing a culture of cooperation and partnership will build on their employees' individual strengths. When there are successful teams, the cumulative result is greater than the sum of the individual effort. There are a range of strategies that can promote team orientation, from team building and diversity seminars to retreats, merit programs that recognize and accept team-oriented activities and processes that encourage project teams.

Organizations that cultivate a team culture have identified and reward team players based on the proposition of Mach and Baruch's (2015). Traits that differentiate team players are the ability to reach consensus and include others in decision-making, to connect openly and honestly, to care for fellow team members, responsible for disputes, and attempting to understand other points of view. Such characteristics are sometimes classified in merit rating systems and become acceptance criteria, promotions or remedial training. Those with an entrepreneurial spirit and competitive drive can also contribute valuable skills and insights to a team effort (Kraiczy, Hack & Kellermanns, 2015). However, Yang and Wang (2014) argued that the team spirit can sometimes be undermined if those strong personalities are grappling with conflict, rivalry, and confidence issues. It may be beneficial to air grievances and encourage team members to vent their frustrations, however administrative guidance and counseling may be important to reinforce the need for individuals to set aside their personal grievances and come together towards a common objective.

Finally, motivation often provides a measure of employee engagement. In order feeling good at their jobs and working optimally, most workers need encouragement (Chen, Hsieh & Chem 2014). Many workers are motivated by money while others are personally driven by appreciation and bonuses. Levels of motivation within the workforce impact directly on productivity of employees. Workers who are inspired and enthusiastic about their work perform their obligations to the best of their ability and as a consequence increase in production numbers (Ganta, 2014).

Apparently, some workers are inspired to fulfill personal and professional goals by feeling a sense of accomplishment and success (Gerhart & Fang, 2015). Most employees are driven and self-disciplined. Incentive and bonuses have little impact on workers who only feel motivated when they are confident in their abilities and connect personally with their position within the company. For the sake of the personal challenge their work provides, these individuals perform productively.

In addition, Olafsen, Halvari, Forest and Deci (2015) many employees have said their employers need recognition in order to produce quality work. Acknowledgment and compensation programs for workers recognize employees who are doing their jobs well. Recognizing a job done well helps the employees feel comfortable and inspires them to do good things. Deci and Ryan (2014) added that by measuring progress and providing feedback on how the progress has been over time, the employers appreciate employees.

Entrepreneurial Marketing

The idea of entrepreneurial marketing was developed some three decades ago at the interface between two distinct areas: marketing and entrepreneurship (Hills, & Hultman, 2013). It is distinct from traditional marketing, since the latter is typically customer focused (Mahr, Lievens, Blazevic, 2014) whereas, entrepreneurial marketing requires product creativity involving an entrepreneurial mind-set (Fiore et al., 2013).

Entrepreneurial marketing can be attributed to marketing works and entrepreneurial advocates who examine how different individuals and even management teams cope with risk and build value in the market by creative and constructive use of resources (Toghraee, Rezvani, Mobaraki, & Farsi, 2017). The new marketing strategy has not replaced the traditional marketing mix. Instead it has enhanced the way businessmen view it and apply it.

Entrepreneurial and business focus was attributed a positive impact on firm success (Long, 2013). Another argument presented by Hallböck and Gabrielsson (2013) that entrepreneurial marketing can lead to better results because it allows not only creative and constructive marketing management, but also opens marketing practices to new methods. There is a high rate of acceptance of marketing concepts in business practices worldwide and the subsequent growth of Entrepreneurial Marketing (Nwaizugbu & Anukam, 2014).

Small firms have established entrepreneurial marketing as a tool. One explanation for this is that large-scale corporations have restricted flexibility in pursuing an entrepreneurial marketing approach; (Hallböck and Gabrielsson, 2013). As such, it further investigates the various variables which influence entrepreneurial marketing in the context of small and medium-sized enterprises. The researcher had been able to identify four components of entrepreneurial marketing from the different readings. These are positive focus, inspired motivation, risk management and generating value.

The first observed variable is proactive orientation, which is defined as the company's strategic position in introducing new business offerings, not fearing risks and exploring new products or services and markets while maintaining a positive outlook in terms of dealing with market opportunities as opposed to its rivals (Stenholm, Pukkinen, & Heinonen, 2016). The creative essence of positive orientation is likely to result in organizational success, as theorized by Lamore, Berkowitz, and Farrington (2013).

Proactive orientation is consistent with the various dimensions of entrepreneurship that El-Annan (2013) defined, including creativity, positive attitude, risk-taking and vision because entrepreneurship is continuously engaged in solving problems and challenges, proactive people who are willing to act in a way that improves their environment are more likely than their counterparts to become entrepreneurs (El-Annan, 2013). While, Barrales-Molina, Martínez-López, and Gázquez-Abad (2014) say that proactive market orientation is more of a marketing skill. Lamore, Berkowitz, & Farrington (2013) found in their analysis that market performance is positively correlated with proactive business orientation.

The next variable observed considered is an opportunity driven. Entrepreneurship practices were divided into two specific categories such as-necessity and opportunity driven. Necessity entrepreneurship is primarily focused on needs; while opportunity entrepreneurship operates primarily on the basis of voluntary engagement or specific market opportunities (Suchart, 2017). Several authors argue that the motivation of an owner to start and run a business has an impact on their firm's growth (Zall, Faghih, Ghotbi & Sahar, 2013).

A business developed to take advantage of a market opportunity is expected to have a higher propensity to develop than a business for which the main drivers are factors such as unemployment, discontent with current employment or reasons for personal lifestyle (Zall, Faghih, Ghotbi, & Sahar, 2013). The definition of opportunities is based on market imperfections that are waiting for their sustainable profit potential to be exploited (Holmes & Jorlov, 2015). Entrepreneurial opportunities exist in the midst of environmental change (Wang, Ellinger, & Jim Wu, 2013), and such awareness of that potential depends on an individual's innovation success (Valliere, 2013). It becomes part of the creative process for the marketer to extend its scope beyond current markets while maintaining an ongoing emphasis and monitoring the world. Once an opportunity is found, which is eased by continuous learning and adaptation, it is up to the entrepreneurial marketer to exploit this opportunity (Holmes & Jorlov, 2015).

To further discuss, entrepreneurship often includes looking for opportunities (Kuratko & Audretsch, 2013) and the success of a firm may be attributed to the willingness of a firm to search for promising opportunities. As Zall, Faghih, Ghotbi, & Sahar (2013) findings show, a positive relationship exists between opportunities-driven entrepreneurship and business growth as well as growth expectations. This can be due to the proposition that retaining an opportunity-driven market outlook allows the company to keep up with its competitive edge (Kuratko & Audretsch, 2013).

Nevertheless, entrepreneurship is not always motivated by opportunities entrepreneurship is driven by needs in some countries (Simón-Moya, Revuelto-Taboada, & Guerrero, 2014). The same writers reported that undertaking practices are influenced by factors such as economy and institutional climate. Whereas, it cannot be denied that there are need-driven entrepreneurs, there is also much evidence showing that incentives are based even by informal sector entrepreneurs (Williams, & Youssef, 2014).

Under entrepreneurial marketing another observed variable is risk management. Any business venture is vulnerable to various forms of risk. In small and medium-sized businesses various types of threats have also been reported (Falkner, & Hiebl, 2015). In reality, Bromiley, McShane, Nair, & Rustambekov, (2015) recommend looking at Enterprise Risk Management as a new approach to risk management. This aspect of managing an enterprise is critical because this helps the entrepreneur to recognise threats that could potentially cause the venture to fail (Bank & Brustbauer, 2014).

While considered fragile, small and medium-sized enterprises are also resilient and fairly easy to manage, so adjusting to change is simpler for these businesses (Lavia López and Hiebl, 2014). Although they are sensitive to change, SMEs have limited funding reserves. It leaves them vulnerable to different risks (Burgstaller and Wagner, 2015). Therefore, due to limited resources, many SMEs do not implement risk management in their company (Marcelino-Sádaba, Pérez-Ezcurdia, Lazcano, & Villanueva, 2014).

Identifying the potential risks that can impact the business' performance is crucial, and it must be at the top of the management obligation asserted by Marcelino-Sádaba, Pérez-Ezcurdia, Lazcano, and Villanueva (2014). They argued that once the risks are identified, mitigating steps can be taken to mitigate the identified risks. Brustbauer, (2016) was able to identify two strategies which were used by SMEs to tackle risks. Those are the active and passive strategies. SMEs' strategies rely on their solutions, which results in a passive approach to a defensive strategy while the active approach results in an offensive strategy. Whatever approach they implement, what is important is that the risk is established, steps to be taken are described and activities are adequately controlled, this helps to ensure the SME's survival (Verbano, & Venturini, 2013).

There are also other propositions that help small and medium-sized enterprises tackle risk management issues, including the use of social capital to discuss risk management capacity building enablers, especially to enterprises with no formal structure and knowledge (Gao, Sung, & Zhang, 2013). Entrepreneurs have been described as self-reliant individuals willing to take the risks (Goffee, & Scase, 2015). However, various entrepreneurs have different levels of risk-taking willingness, it has been noted that motivated entrepreneurs are more willing to take risks than those driven by necessity (Block, Sandner, & Spiegel, 2015). The willingness to take the risk then coincides with the ability to manage the potential risks. As postulated by Belas, Kljucnikov, Vojtovic and Sobekova-Majková (2015), financial risk management is one of the important skills that SMEs need because their growth and development depends on their ability to determine where to allocate their remunerations.

The last observed variable considered in entrepreneurial marketing is value creation. One of the main topics in entrepreneurial marketing is value creation (Ozdemir, 2013). It is the process of creating value-in-use that customers experience (Ozdemir, 2013). Moreover, it is also the process wherein the customers go through in creating value-in-use and the process of creating value-in-use that customers experienced (Grönroos & Voima, 2013). Looking into its management is important because it has been observed that the businesses which have been able to create value over an extended period of time have been able to adapt and refresh the company's models successfully and further sustain their value creation (Achtenhagen, Melin, & Naldi, 2013).

The goal of any marketing endeavor has long been to create value for customers (Gummerus, 2013). Value creation has been given a great deal of attention because it is important for strategic success (Tantalo & Priem, 2016), as well as being connected to intellectual capital and business models (Beattie & Smith, 2013). The acquisition of customer information has allowed various companies to turn them into services that could add to the perceived value of customers, particularly in their experience (Sorensen & Jensen, 2015)

Further research into value creation is important as it is not only crucial to the success of different approaches; it has also been identified as having an effect on the business performance in general. For one it is known as a core determinant of the enterprise's innovation operation (O'Cass & Sok, 2013), it emphasizes that the principle of value creation in an enterprise is a deciding variable in the innovation operation of a company. Nuryakin, Aryanto and Setiawan (2018) study revealed that value development has a positive impact on the success of the enterprise.

The link between value creation and the company's success is that value creation plays a major role in producing new goods and services (Viljakainen & Toivonen 2014; Sorensen & Jensen 2015). Besides the significant correlation between value creation and firm efficiency, the association between value creation and market factor is also important, differentiation sources and varying sales models (Vermeer, 2016). Creation of value and business marketing are strongly interrelated (Mengting, & Zhang, 2015).

The basis of value formation may be exposed by value propositions put forward by a business organization to attract consumers (Mengting & Zhang, 2015). Due to the differing definitions of value, various kinds of value exist (Costanza, de Groot, Sutton, Van der Ploeg, Anderson, Kubiszewski & Turner, 2014). Value can therefore be produced when product attributes, such as design, service, address specific customer needs (Gummerus, 2013), whereas it can be generated simply by reducing monetary costs and by offering advantages at the level of customers or stakeholders Su, Li, Huang, Huang, Shuang and Wang (2013).

Value creation also plays an important role in developing relationships, especially between suppliers and customers (Kowalkowski, Witell & Gustafsson, 2013). Not only would it ensure that consumers are satisfied as it also paves the way to maintain a successful relationship with the company's suppliers (Tescari & Brito, 2016). Furthermore, Tescari and Brito (2016) describe two value sources within their model. Another that both buyer and supplier make, and the other is the inherent value that comes from the strengths as well as buyer and seller's resources. For better understand how this affects the success of small and medium-sized businesses, it is important to examine more the value creation.

Employee Empowerment

Definitions of empowerment often differ widely between scholars. Many studies describe empowerment as an intrinsic motivation for the job (Dust, Resick & Mawritz, 2014; Fernandez & Moldogaziev, 2013; Joo & Lim, 2013) or a person-environment-fit motivation (Farzaneh Dehghanpour Farashah & Kazemi, 2014). Empowerment has been described in other literature as perceptions (Men & Stacks, 2013) and as commitment-based designs (Spreitzer, 1996).

Scholars also have described empowerment for the transition of power or authority in terms of job structure (Armache, 2013).

Over the past few years, empowerment has become an important trend in general management. There is general encouragement to allow workers to have ample flexibility in their work-definition and authority to apply the full range of skills to the overall objectives. Recently, in the specific project management setting, the utility of empowerment has begun to be recognized (Elnaga & Imran, 2014). Some authors (Rutland, 1994; Walker, 2015) addressed its importance both among companies, leading to an increase in structures such as partnership (which implies a degree of trust between companies) and, more applicable to this paper, within a company. He addresses the value of motivation for workers as a differentiating factor between companies (Boussaleem, 2015).

Empowerment is also described as the act of giving people the opportunity to take decisions in the workplace by increasing their decision-making autonomy (Jha, 2015). Empowerment has also been defined as dismantling conventional hierarchical structures (Fatima Iqbal, & Imran, 2013). Empowerment gives staff the right to make decisions about customer service from a business perspective. Throughout industrial and organizational psychology and management, empowerment is the enhancement of employee independence within their jobs or increased participation resulting in increased decision-making more broadly within the organization's wider agenda and priorities (Fock, Hui, Au & Bond, 2013).

It is (Rodell, 2013) highlighted the organizational dimension of empowerment, calling it the process of providing workers with the required guidance and skills to allow autonomous decision-making including transparency and accountability within appropriate parameters that is part of an organizational culture. It is widely believed that a motivated and dedicated workforce is necessary for the successful functioning of modern organizations (Lin & Tseng, 2013; Raub & Robert, 2013). Empowered employees are a source of new ideas and creativity that improve efficiency and productivity if time, training and resources are allocated to the process and employees are encouraged to develop a sense of self-efficiency, job fulfillment, trust, self-assurance and job meaningfulness (Kahre, Ahmadi, & Hashemi, 2011).

Meanwhile, any effect of employee empowerment on workplace efficiency depends on some of the effects of behavior (Bose, 2018). This variable promotes a worker's dedication to the company as suggested and found by Sharma and Kirkman (2015). Consequently, there has been a major increase in employee performance for increasing unit shift in employee empowerment (Njoroge, 2018). Empowerment is observable by two constructs. One of these is the psychological empowerment framework which has gained much attention from researchers in many business fields (Malik, Chughtai, Iqbal & Ramzan, 2013).

Meaningfulness is one of the indicators of empowerment. Meaningfulness put forward competent individuals that respect career goals according to their personal ideals and standards; work is considered important in their value system and they believe they are relevant when involved in the organization's activities (Rosso, Dekas, Wrzesniewski, 2010). Specifically, meaningfulness is the intrinsic treatment of the individual for a given task, and it involves the importance of the task objective measured in relation to the individual's own value system, values and/or expectations (Fernandez & Moldogaziev, 2013). In other words, the sense of meaning or purpose derives from a match between the needs of one's working role and one's beliefs, values, and behaviors (Sharma & Kirkman 2015). Lack of meaningfulness is thought to result in feelings of apathy and alienation (Joo & Lim, 2013), which harm job motivation and quality of work performance (Fock et al., 2013).

For meaningfulness the best theoretical case was made for a positive relationship to job satisfaction (Namasivayam, Guchait, & Lei, 2014). It has already been emphasized in the late 1950s that the degree to which an individual considers that work is personally meaningful is an essential precondition for job gratification (Saif & Saleh, 2013). This idea was echoed by Cicolini, Comparcini and Simonetti (2014) adding meaningfulness of work as a crucial path to happiness at work. Individuals who consider their employment to be important and valuable are more comfortable at work than those who consider their employment to be of little interest. By comparison, low levels of sense were related to workplace apathy, and thus lower rates of work satisfy (Jose & Mampilly, 2014). More theoretical arguments build upon the notion of personal meaning satisfaction by Wang & Lee (2009). Through this viewpoint, job satisfaction stems from the belief that one's job fulfills the desired work values or enables them to be fulfilled. This value fulfillment is in line with the element of empowerment (Hooker, 2015).

Competence is also another empowerment measure. Once people are competent, they feel self-efficacy or they feel skilled and have enough aptitude and experience to do a good job. Not only are capable people feeling skilled, yet they feel comfortable and competent in their work (Harrison & Waite, 2015; Lorinkova, Pearsall & Sims, 2013). The feeling of individual greatness is present and further expects that in the event that they are going to experience new difficulties, they ought to learn and thrive (Soltani & Sanatyzadeh, 2013). A few writers hypothesize this trademark is the most significant part of mental strengthening for it is simply the inclination adequacy which produces steadiness and attempt to play out the troublesome works (Wang and Zhang, 2013).

Competence is "the degree to which a person can skillfully carry out task activities when attempting" (Fernandez & Moldogaziev, 2013). It can be interpreted as self-efficacy (Bandura, 2000) particular to one's work, and should be differentiated from self-esteem as the former is confined to a position of work as opposed to the latter being construed as global effectiveness (Martela & Riecki, 2018). Nonetheless, self-efficacy, the core variable of social cognitive theory (Bandura 1986), has proved to be "one of the most focused phenomena in contemporary psychological research" (Boussaleem, 2015), as evidenced by evidence that over the past 25 years it has been tested in more than 10,000 investigations (Judge, Jackson, Shaw, Scott & Rich et al., 2007). Accumulated evidence suggests a positive relationship between self-and results related to the job (Avey, Luthans & Youssef, 2010). Research indicates that self-efficacy, as a

positive psychological power that underlines the newly emerging central structure of positive psychological capital (Cascio&Luthans, 2014) can be reinforced and encouraged in four very different ways: mastery of activities, modeling, persuasion and/or input, and physiological and/or psychological anticipation and wellbeing (Bandura, 2010). In summary, in the terms of Bandura (1986), competence is tantamount to belief in organization, personal control, or expectation of effort-performance.

Self-determination also constitutes an indicator of empowerment. Employees who are capable feel responsibility and accountability for their actions (Rasouli, Montazeri, Nekouei, & Zahedi, 2013). They feel independent in carrying out their responsibilities; they can make decisions about their job and have ample authority with regard to the direction, time and pace of their task (Wong , Humborstad, Nerstad & Dysvik, 2014). Examples in this field include decision making about the methods of performing the job or deciding the amount of effort required to perform the tasks (GanjiNia et al., 2013). Self-determination implies causal responsibility for the actions of an individual. It is the view of the employee about flexibility in initiating and maintaining job activities and processes (Ameer, Bhatti & Baig, 2014; Degago, 2014).

According to Deci and Ryan (2013) findings self-determination results in learning, engagement in action and resistance to adversity. When there is no self-determination, individuals feel powerless because they are not permitted to take work-related decisions, they deem appropriate (Nazem, Mozaiini & Seifi 2014). In a systematic meta-analysis summarizing the perceived control relationship (including engagement and autonomy) with a variety of outcomes, Gohar,Bashir,Abrar and Asghar (2015) found strong evidence of positive associations with job performance that connects self-determination with effectiveness. Employees typically have more comprehensive knowledge and awareness about their jobs from a cognitive perspective than their employers and are therefore in a stronger position to prepare and schedule jobs and to recognize and overcome barriers to job performance (Nazem et al., 2014). Employees get to learn which habits and job approaches are most successful and how performance could be improved.

The last indicator under employee empowerment is impact. Impact is defined by the degree to which the individual "can affect political, managerial, or operational outcomes at work" (Men & Stacks, 2013), and is the converse of learned helplessness (Boussalem, 2015). In definition, the impact varies from the locus of control; the former is defined by the context of the research (Goncalves, Kostakos, Karapanos, Barreto, Camacho, Tomasic, & Zimmerman, 2014) whereas the latter is considered to be a characteristic of a global personality which endures in situations. Recently (Boussalem, 2015) shows that the motive for effect makes it beneficial for an employer to grant workers flexibility in the choice of effort or assignment.

Impact or approval of the personal outcome is a stage where individuals control the outcomes and the political, public, and operational implications (Abdollahi & Ebrahim, 2011). Capable workers feel that by practicing their job roles they play a significant role in achieving the organizational goals and further can monitor job outcomes and results and have a positive impact on what happens and can cope with constraints and challenges (Rezaie, Saleh, Iman & Jaafar, 2012).

It represents to what degree an individual can affect political, managerial, or organizational outcomes at work (Luoh, Tsaur & Tang, 2014). As Lee and Koh (2001) have pointed out, the general notion of impact was examined under various labels, including learned helplessness (Silvet, 2013) and locus of control (Lefcourt, 2014). Impact is the converse of learned helplessness (Goncalves et al., 2014), but it is distinct from the locus of control. The internal locus of control is a feature of a general personality, while impact endures with the work context (Degago et al., 2014).

Although the impact aspect of empowerment in the literature has received less attention than the other aspects, theory suggests that success should be linked positively to it. If individuals believe they can affect the structure they are placed in, that they can influence organizational outcomes and have been seen as more successful (Rasouli et al., 2013). By comparison, people who do not believe they can make a difference are less likely to try as hard in their work, and are therefore often seen as less successful. Finally, concentrating on the effect aspect, it was found by Luoh et al. (2014) to be correlated with a lack of withdrawal from difficult situations and high performance.

Employee Job Performance

Performance is a broad multidimensional construct aimed at achieving outcomes and has a strong link to an organization's strategic goals (Obicci, 2015). Employee efficiency is the job-related activities, and how well workers conducted those tasks. Usually not every employee action is subsumed under the principle of efficiency. Employee's conduct must contribute to the organization's goal such as improving the organization's revenue and making profit. Job performance is defined as the total expected value for organizing the discrete behavioral episodes a person performs over a standard period of time (Gondal & Husain, 2013). Thus, the performance is determined by the judgmental and evaluative processes of the actions but not by the actions themselves and after a period of time it is carried out by the employee.

Employee performance means just the same as work performance. There are two dimensions of employee actions found in job performance, role performance and qualitative performance (Ensslin, Ensslin, Back & Lacerda, 2013). Task performance is the employee's activity that provides indirect support to the core technological processes of the organization, directly involved in the production of goods or service activities. Job performance means employee using their unique skills and knowledge to help the key technological processes of the company. Management must understand the importance of employee performance, and take steps to cultivate and empower workers to perform well. If the organization's output is successful, it can lead the market and take advantage of the opportunities available on the market (Chei, Yee, Men & Bee, 2014).

Employee efficiency is critical for providing the restaurants with quality services, which in turn raises customer satisfaction (Karatepe, 2013). Restaurant staff at all levels serve the restaurant and therefore a guest who feels ignored or treated poorly has no intention of staying there longer or revisiting the restaurant next time. Hanzaee and Mirvaisi (2013) claimed that the importance and quality of the restaurant services are decided by the customers, the staff responsible for providing the guest experience should not only be qualified but also driven to meet the quality of the service and the value demands of the guests. The HR supervisors and the restaurateurs have a vital role to play in educating and inspiring restaurant staff to provide exceptional service experiences to customers. The effective ways to motivate restaurant employees or workers are adequate compensation, financial rewards, appreciation schemes and among others used by restaurant owners (Karatepe, 2013).

Stress is an indicator of performance at the workplace. Over the years, stress has been characterized in varying ways. According to (Ivancevich, Konapske & Matteson, 2006; Awino, Ogutu & Musyoka, 2018) stress is scientifically characterized as the reaction of an individual to the outcomes of external environmental conditions, which put undue psychological, behavioral, and physiological pressure on that individual. It involves how a person responds to outside pressures. It is characterized as a dynamic situation in which a person faces an opportunity, constraints or demand related to what he or she wants and for which the outcome is viewed as both uncertain and important (Ekienabor (2016).

Published in The World Health Organization (WHO) defines occupational stress as the reaction that people may have when faced with work demands and pressures that don't suit their knowledge and abilities and challenge their ability to cope Semmer (2007),. According to Sohail and Rehman (2015), stress is simply an employee's reaction when certain job demands, stresses and professional aspects do not conform to their level of knowledge that creates or poses a challenge and a danger to the abilities of the employee, which in turn would create a life-long struggle in terms of being employed on the job.

Service industry is a labor-intensive industry that needs customer interaction. The high level of burnout of staff is linked to the high level of work stress and has a negative impact on organizational engagement, commitment to work and efficiency (Chiang & Hsieh, 2012). The basis of quality of service at the accommodation industry depends on the performance of workers providing direct, face-to-face customer service (Karatepe, 2013). Although this is acknowledged, long working hours, lack of work safety, unpredictable and inflexible scheduling of work, position tension, heavy workload, restricted weekend leaves, unreasonable work requirements, low wages, staff turnover, poor customer behaviour, and inadequate training programs are common problems in the accommodation industry and create pressure on staff (Altintas & Turanligil, 2018).

It is also reported that there is a lack of support policies in accommodation businesses to help families, a shortage of resources for growth, and ignorance of staff ideas in the decision-making process result in high stress levels (Karatepe & Karadas, 2015). In addition, staff that provides face-to-face, direct customer support may also have marital problems due to heavy workload (Karatepe & Talebzadeh, 2016). These issues suggest that accommodation companies lack contemporary strategies for handling human resources (Karatepe & Kilic, 2015).

A further measure of job performance is the working environment. Work environment defined as behavior and that contending with the activities and results of employees. The work environment and the employees are interrelated (Akinyele, 2010). Once workers have a good working environment, they work harder and improve performance.

According to Akinyele (2010), the willingness of employees to share knowledge with each other depends on how they use the environment. It helps companies increase income performance, productivity level etc. In addition, the work environment is characterized as the interrelationship of employees in their workplace that can be divided into the social, technological and economic elements. The three aspects consist of a range of factors including culture of the organization, structure of the organization, types of management and so on (Salunke, 2015).

Based on Razak, Ma'amor, and Hassan (2016), companies need to provide a healthy working environment to ensure that workers have a good working condition thereby improving their job satisfaction and ensuring employees have a better quality of work. In addition, several researches explored the effect on individual and team efficiency of work environment variables such as workstation height and thickness partitions, furniture dimensions and the volume and availability of file and work storage (Naharuddin & Sadegi, 2013). Study concluded that the work characteristics and working conditions have an effect on job performance in manufacturing environment (Kahya, 2007). Restaurant-sector surveys have shown poor working conditions in the restaurant market (Jayaweera, 2015).

Kaya (2015) suggested that the work environment consists not only of physical elements such as architecture, equipment, appliances, but also of the psychosocial atmosphere in nature. Referring to Spector (1997) as quoted in Raziq and Maulabakhsh (2015), the work environment consists of workplace safety, job security, decision-making authorization, co-worker relationship, and recognition. Balance of work life is also an aspect of the work environment (Lazar, Osoian, & Ratiu, 2010; Al Sumaiti, 2010). The researchers claimed that they have to make an effort to maintain a positive work atmosphere for their employees in order for a company to retain its employees and sustain itself in the competitive market.

According to the Maslow Needs Theory, physiological needs are viewed as the most basic necessity that is important to any human being and hence put at the lowest level of the hierarchy. Subsequently, the needs to be met were the need for protection, belonging, and appreciation. Such employee expectations have to be met at the workplace. This helps boost their job satisfaction, which eventually increases their dedication and efficiency (Salunke, 2015).

Another indicator of job performance is workload. Workload refers to the amount of work an employee is being asked to do. A number of researchers identified a positive relationship between the intention to work load, stress and turnover intention (Qureshi, Iftikhar, Abbas, Hassan, Khan, & Zaman, 2013). Oplatka (2017) found that this study

implies that substantial relationships between workload and stress and stress and turnover play an arbitrary function between workload and turnover intentions. A heavy long term workload may affect the physical or mental health, efficiency, or productivity of an employee. Therefore, it has been shown that heavy workloads have a negative impact on productivity (Feng & Cao, 2017) certainly contribute to a stressed state and cause pressure, injuries or illness. High turnover of workers brings with it the problems of both high labor costs and quality problems that harm a company's performance and development (Flook, Goldberg, Pinger, Bonus & Davidson 2013). Accordingly, Suarathana and Riana (2016) and Qureshiet al. (2013) recommended that managers actively monitor employee workloads to minimize turnover.

Ali and Farooqi (2014) examined the impact of workload on job satisfaction, the effect of job satisfaction on employee performance and employee engagement in the public sector and the finding that work stress had a significant negative relationship with job satisfaction and employee satisfaction had a greater positive relationship with employee performance and a very positive relationship with employee engagement. Portoghese, Galletta, Coppola, Finco, and Campagna (2014) conducted burnout and workload research among health care workers and demonstrated a significant workload association with higher job exhaustion. Health care workers were more depressed when they did not have job flexibility in response to higher workload rates.

Finally, salaries are also an important indicator of employment success. Salary can be characterized as a fixed amount of money paid to a worker that is typically assessed on a monthly and annual basis, not on an hourly basis, as opposed to wages; salary is a fixed amount of money or compensation paid to an employer in exchange for the work done (Pfeifer, 2014). It is rather surprising to note that self-equity is considered to be less important, as a company can do little about the perception of inequity among its workers with regard to their financial needs or their historical pay evolution. Berri, Leeds and Von Allmen (2015) address how companies offer their employees upward-sloping wage profiles to prevent shirking Ejeremo and Schubert (2014) indicates that businesses use upward-sloping profiles as a way to discourage movers from applying for jobs. Hoon and Parent (2013) demonstrated how work matching could produce upward-sloping salary profiles under imperfect information.

Motivation is seen as the amount of effort the seller wants to expend on each of the events or duties connected with his work, such as searching for potential new customers, arranging sales presentations and reporting (Robinson, Stamps, Marshall & Lamb, 2015) monetary rewards are the primary motivator of the marketing effort and the pay package is the basic motivator, whereas other financial incentives, such as bonuses and competitions, in some circumstances only induce effort beyond that generated by the basic plan (Fatima, 2017). Many individuals who are competitive and relatively high in financial motivation inevitably pursue such occupations as salesmen, the typical salesman is financially motivated far more strongly than the average employee in his organization (Zablah, Carlson, Donovan, Maxham III & Brown, 2016).

1.5 Correlation between Measures

Employee engagement plays a significant role for the enhancement of employee's job performance (Fernet, Trépanier, Austin, Gagné, & Forest, 2015). Both directly and indirectly influence the positive correlation between the degree of work commitment and job performance of employees (Van Wingerden, Derks & Bakker, 2017). Nonetheless, almost every labor force segment is continually viewed as more competitive (Bakker & Albrecht, 2018) because workers feel positive emotions that broaden their thought, make them more concentrated and more involved in their work (Shantz et al., 2013).

In this analysis, employee engagement and job performance contribute to the Job Demands-Resources Model (Schaufeli & Bakker, 2004). It is believed that all jobs contain "demand" and "resources" (Bakker & Demerouti, 2008). Work engagement, for example, is associated with attitude indicators such as organizational engagement (Hakanen, Bakker & Schaufeli, 2006; Hakanen, Schaufeli & Ahola, 2008) and turnover intention (Schaufeli & Bakker, 2004), while managers and co-workers ranked higher in-role performance employees than others (Halbesleben & Wheeler, 2008).

Work engagement at the level of the unit of employment has led to greater innovativeness through greater personal initiative (Hakanen, Perhoniemi, & Toppinen-Tanner, 2008). However, the quality of services assessed by the customer has been positively affected by work participation among restaurant staff (Salanova, Agut, & Peiró, 2005). In a study conducted at a dairy fast-food restaurant, Xanthopoulou, Bakker, Demerouti and Schaufeli (2009), it was found that the daily available work resources among the serving employees had a positive effect on their financial returns for each shift as a result of their dedication to work. Hence, workers are committed to produce more than performance to higher productivity (Sacks, 2006).

In restaurants, entrepreneurship results in positive macroeconomic outcomes and can lead to better performance in existing organizations Lee, Singal and Kang, 2013. Entrepreneurship and marketing have been two well-established scientific areas for the last 25 years, which are central in business studies with a widespread belief that successful entrepreneurship requires marketing as an entrepreneurial approach to successful marketing needs (Hills & LaForge 1992). So these study hinged on the proposition of Hills and Hultman (2013).

Marketing and entrepreneurship were investigated to have a clear interrelationship, meaning they influence the effect on performance of each other. Micro and small businesses have a different marketing approach relative to large companies (De Jong & Freel, 2000); they do not have the same resources as big firms, which mean that marketing principles developed in large firms are not universally appropriate. Pro-activeness as one of the metrics of entrepreneurial marketing shows a strong positive correlation with company success (Lumpkin & Dess, 2001) whereas; innovativeness is a vital determinant of company's performance (Cooper, 2000).

There was significant change in employee performance for every unit shift in the employee empowerment practice (Agugustain, Agu & Okocha, 2019). Empowered staff has the ability to be creative and ensure good performance (Mullins, 2007). Empowerment of employees today is one of the primary causes of increasing quality in the workplace (Robbins, Crino & Fredendall, 2002; Kimolo, 2013). Similarly, Lennick and Kiel (2011) pointed out when people in the organization realize how their work contributes to the company's success, morale and productivity typically increase. In addition to this, Byars and Rue, 2000; Kimolo (2013) stressed the value of company leaders understanding exactly what is expected of them and the yardstick by which their success and outcomes is calculated.

The relationship between employee empowerment and job performance was subsequently based on the proposition of Hechanova et al. (2006). Consequently, there is a relationship among Filipino service workers between psychological empowerment, job satisfaction, and efficiency. The study found a strong link with success in the psychological empowerment. One of the studies that explicitly support the relationship between empowerment and firm results was provided by Hitt, Bierman, Shimizu, and Kochhar's (2001). In a sample of professional companies, this study found a positive relationship between human capital based on intellectual ability, expertise and social capital and firm results.

The literature gathered in this research has greatly helped the researcher appreciate the course of the study. Besides this, the literature supported the establishment of acceptability of variables and their indicators. The researcher acknowledged that job performance is a rapidly evolving and growing field of research. A growing amount of study is using the output of employees as a powerful theoretical context, some of which is used for empirical analysis. Relevant studies for the creation and establishment of a well-managed restaurant were also considered primarily by research aimed at identifying the motives, expectations and reasons why restaurant owners and managers are still searching and developing suitable strategies. Nonetheless, there are still a bunch of gaps in study and literature that can be addressed to encourage new approaches and viewpoints that can be recognized in the industry, and also in the field of business and management analysis that can be effective in filling those gaps.

1.6 Theoretical Framework

This study used several theoretical premises and frameworks. Employee engagement and job performance were linked to Job Demands-Resources Model (Schaufeli & Bakker, 2004) The JDR-WE model (Bakker & Demerouti, 2008) assumes that all jobs include 'requests' and 'resources' A series of studies were conducted which provided initial support for the JDR-WE model's motivational mechanism (Bakker & Demerouti, 2008). Work engagement is associated with attitudinal indicators such as organizational engagement and turnover plan, as Schaufeli (2013) confirmed. In addition, the research into how engagement mediates the relationship between job resources and job performance found that increased employment resources resulted in higher work commitment and lower subsequent absenteeism (Schaufeli, Bakker & Van Rhenen, 2009).

Other research used the JDR-WE model to analyze different performance indicators. The self-reported medical errors were thus negatively correlated with the presence of physicians (Prins, Van, Heijden, Weebers, Bakker, Weil, Jacobs & Domofrio, 2009) while supervisors and co- highly engaged employees are ranked higher on in-role tests than others (Halbesleben & Wheeler, 2008). Work-unit-level engagement contributed to greater innovativeness through increased personal initiative (Hakanen et al., 2008). In addition, work engagement among restaurant staff positively affected the quality of services assessed by customers (Salanova, Agut, & Peiró, 2005).

Conclusively, in a diary experiment in a fast food restaurant, Xanthopoulou, Bakker, Demerouti and Schaufeli (2009) found that the daily available work resources among the serving staff had a positive impact on their financial yields for each job change as a function of their work engagement. To sum up, there are clear indications that performance indicators such as absenteeism, customer satisfaction, in-role and extra-role efficiency, and financial returns indirectly correlate with job characteristics (employment demands and resources) through the well-being of employees (burnout and commitment), as predicted by the JD-R model.

The relationship of entrepreneurial marketing and employee job performance washed to the proposition of Hills and Hultman (2013). Marketing and entrepreneurship were examined to have a strong interrelationship, meaning they influence the effect on performance of each other. Entrepreneurship and marketing have been two well-established scientific areas for the past 25 years which are fundamental to business studies. Pursuant to Hills and LaForge (1992) that there is widespread belief that successful business requires marketing as an entrepreneurial approach to successful marketing. Entrepreneurial marketing identifies micro, small and medium sized business marketing companies (Harms, Luck, Kraus & Walsh, 2014). Entrepreneurial marketing takes place in an organization of any size, but the importance for small and large businesses could be different (Bjerke & Hultman, 2004).

The employees of businesses in various specialized positions contribute directly and indirectly to the marketing of firms. The typical marketing strategy model within the Managerial School includes the following steps: market analysis, business priorities, strategic marketing planning, marketing planning and implementation (Zeriti, Robson & Spyropoulou & Leonidou, 2014). In conformity with Armstrong and Baron (2007) that managing the performance of workers and aligning their priorities promotes the successful execution of strategic and organizational objectives thus, increases the profitability of a business. Direct financial benefits that may be correlated with the success of a company include; sales growth decreased operating expenses, and reduced project overruns among others.

Subsequently, the relationship of employee empowerment and employee job performance was based on the proposition of Hechanova, Alampay and Franco, (2006). Accordingly, there is a relationship among Filipino service workers between psychological empowerment, job satisfaction, and efficiency. The study found a positive link with

success in the psychological empowerment. Subramony, (2009), provides one of the studies which directly support the relationship between empowerment and firm results. This study is supported by Hiitt, Bierman, Shimizu and Kochhar (2001) who in a sample of professional organizations found a positive relationship between human capital centered on intellectual skills, experience, and social capital and firm results.

Using correlation and regression analysis, the relationship between employee empowerment and employee performance, as tested by Mehrabani and Shajari (2013), revealed that empowerment strongly influences employee performance. In addition, Celik, Cakici, and Celik (2014) analyzed the influence of employee empowerment on organizational creativity and innovation through regression analysis, and found that employee empowerment has a significant impact on organizational creativity and innovation. Meyerson and Dewettinck (2012) examined the relationship between employee empowerment and worker performance using correlation and multiple regression analysis and found that employee empowerment has a significant impact on employee performance.

1.7 Conceptual Framework

The five hypothesized models are composed of two types of latent constructs namely, exogenous and endogenous variables as shown in figures from one to five.

Unobserved variables, Structural Equation Modeling (SEM), are called latent variables, causes, or constructs. A latent variable or factor is calculated indirectly by one or more observed predictor variables representing the factor or shaping it. As with path analyzes, in the Structural Equation Model, independent and dependent variables are labeled exogenous and endogenous variables. Exogenous variables are the variables that affect certain variables and are not influenced by other variables in the model; endogenous variables are the variables that are affected by exogenous and other endogenous variables within the model.

It is possible to observe exogenous and endogenous variables, or latent variables. However, apart from the latent and observed variables, there are residuals error terms associated with each of these which also form a key part of the overall model and it is represented with ϵ or error. The double headed arrows represent the interrelationship or correlation between variables, while the single headed arrow represent causal or direct relationship of latent endogenous variables, latent exogenous variables and measured variables. As shown, the exogenous variables of this study are employee engagement, entrepreneurial marketing and employee empowerment. On the other hand, the endogenous variable is job performance since latent variables are not directly observed, it follows that they are not directly measurable. With this, each latent constructs are associated with multiple measures or observed variables. So, one of the primary interests of this analysis was the magnitude of the regression paths from the latent variable to the observed variables.

The latent employee engagement has five observed variables, namely; emotional engagement, rational identification, compatibility, team orientation and motivation. Emotional engagement includes curiosity, frustration, joy, anxiety, and other affective states, any of which factors may affect learner participation or sustained efforts (Anthony et al., 2017). Rational (thinking) commitment is the extent to which workers believe their self-interest is in the minds of their managers, teams or organizations, whether financial, developmental or professional (Chernyak-Hai & Tziner, 2016). Compatibility is the consistency of the relationship between manager (executive, manager, boss, team leader) and employee impacts significantly on the performance of employees (Arezes, Dinis-Carvalho & Alves, 2015). Team orientation is when companies that emphasize a spirit of cooperation and partnership can draw on the individual strengths of their workers (Guillaume et al., 2017). This is motivated by the fact that employees are inspired and enthusiastic about their jobs, performing their duties to the best of their ability and therefore the production numbers (Ganta, 2014).

Meanwhile, the latent entrepreneurial marketing has six observed variables, namely; proactive orientation, opportunity driven, customer intensity, innovation focused, risk management and value creation. Proactive orientation described as the strategic posture adopted by the company that introduce new market offers and explore new products or services and markets (Stenholm et al., 2016). Opportunity driven is where opportunity entrepreneurship is mainly operating based on voluntary engagement or unique market opportunity (Suchart, 2017) and marketing relationship (Fiore et al., 2013) Innovation-focused is the company's effort to seek new marketing ideas within organizational internal and external activities (Fiore et al., 2013). Risk management is something that needs attention to be given to this aspect of managing a business because this helps the entrepreneur to identify threats that could potentially cause the venture to fail (Bank & Brustbauer 2014). Value creation is the process of creating value-in-use for customers (Grönroos & Voima, 2013).

The latent employee empowerment has also four observed variables, namely: meaningfulness, competence, self-determination and impact. Meaningfulness means competent individuals who value career goals in keeping with their personal values and expectations (Tubbs and Moss, 2000). Competence is the degree to which a person can perform task activities skilfully when attempting to do so (Fernandez & Moldogaziev, 2013). On the other hand, self-determination results in awareness, motivation in action and resilience in the face of adversity (Deci & Ryan, 2013). Impact or approval of personal outcome is a stage in which individuals control the outcomes and the political, public, and operational implications (Abdollahi & Ebrahim, 2011).

Moreover, the latent variable employee job performance is composed of four observed variables, namely: stress, working environment, workload and salary. Stress is scientifically defined as an individual's reaction to the outcomes of the external environment that places undue psychological, behavioral and physiological pressure on that person (Ivancevich et al., 2006; Awinoet al., 2018). Work environment described as behavior and contending with the

activities and results of the employees (Babatunde & Ayodele, 2018). Workload refers to the amount of work an employee is expected to do (Qureshiet al.,2013). Salary can be characterized as a fixed amount of money paid to a worker that is typically assessed on a monthly and annual basis, not on an hourly basis, as opposed to salaries; salary is a fixed amount of money or compensation paid to an employer in exchange for the work done (Pfeifer, 2014).

In this analysis five alternative models have been proposed. The structural equation model allows researchers to analyze a set of interrelated research questions in a single, systematic and detailed analysis by simultaneously modeling the relations between multiple independent and dependent constructs (Gefen, Straub, & Boudreau, 2004). This allows researchers estimate the relationships simultaneously between observed and non-observed variables and the relationships between non-observed variables. It also allows researchers to simultaneously use both constant and categorical observable and latent variables (Hair, Sarstedt, Ringle & Mena,2012).Unobserved variables within Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) are called latent variables, causes, or constructs. A latent variable or factor is determined indirectly by one or more observed indicator variables which reflect the factor or influence it.

Considering the key features of the conceptual model, SEM was chosen as the main statistical method for testing the hypothetical model. A general SEM model also contains two sub model forms, one measuring model and one structural model. The measuring model describes the relationship between a latent variable and observed indicator variables, while the structural model describes the relation between latent variables and measurable factors that are not measurements of latent variables (Byrne, 2016). In addition, the five proposed structural models showed potential causal interaction between exogenous and endogenous influences.

The five hypothesized models are composed of two types of latent constructs namely, exogenous and endogenous variables as shown in Figures one to five (1-5). Hypothesized model 1 illustrates the direct causal relationship between the exogenous variables: employee engagement, entrepreneurial marketing, and employee engagement on the endogenous variable: employees’ job performance. Hypothesized model 2 displays the correlation between employee engagement, entrepreneurial marketing, and employee engagement on their direct causal relationship to employees’ job performance. Hypothesized model 3 is model modification that shows correlation between employee engagement and employee empowerment and their direct causal relationship to employees’ job performance. Hypothesized model 4 is another model modification that presents direct causal relationship to of entrepreneurial marketing to employees’ job performance. Lastly, hypothesized model 5 is also a model modification that depicts direct causal relationship to of employee empowerment to employees’ job performance. See hypothesis model:

Figure 1. A Model showing Direct Causal Relationship of Employee Engagement, Entrepreneurial Marketing, Employee Engagement to Job Performance

LEGEND

Employee Engagement	EMP_EN G	Employee Empowerment	EME_E MP
Emotional Engagement	EE	Meaningfulness	MS
Rational Identification	RI	Competence	CS
Motivation	CY	Self Determination	SD
Team Orientation	TN	Impact	IS
Compatibility	MN		
Entrepreneurial Marketing	ENT_MA R	Job Performance	JOB_PER
Proactive Orientation	PO	Stress	SS
Opportunity Driven	OD	Working Environment	WE
Customer Intensity	CI	Workload	WD
Innovation Focused	IF	Salary	SY
Risk Management	RM		
Value Creation	VC		

Figure 2. A Model showing Correlation between Employee Engagement, Entrepreneurial Marketing, Employee Empowerment and the Direct Causal Relationship to Job Performance

Figure 3. A Model showing Correlation between Employee Engagement and Employee Empowerment and their Direct Causal Relationship to Job Performance

LEGEND

Employee Engagement	EMP_EG	Employee Empowerment	EMP_EMP
Emotional Engagement	EE	Meaningfulness	MS
Rational Identification	RI	Competence	CS
Compatibility	CY	Self Determination	SD
Team Orientation	TN	Impact	IS
Motivation	MN		
Entrepreneurial Marketing	ENT_MAR	Job Performance	JOB_PER
Proactive Orientation	PO	Stress	SS
Opportunity Driven	OD	Working Environment	WE
Customer Intensity	CI	Workload	WD
Innovation Focused	IF	Salary	SY
Risk Management	RM		
Value Creation	VC		

LEGEND

Employee Engagement	EMP_ENG	Employee Empowerment	EMP_EMP
Motivation	MN	Meaningfulness	MS
Team Orientation	TN	Competence	CS
Compatibility	CY	Self Determination	SD
Rational Identification	RI	Impact	IS
Emotional Engagement	EE		
Job Performance	JOB_PER		
Stress	SS		
Working Environment	WE		
Workload	WD		
Salary	SY		

Figure 4. A Model showing Correlation between Employee Engagement and Entrepreneurial Marketing and their Direct Causal Relationship to Job Performance

LEGEND

Employee Engagement	EMP_ENG	Job Performance	JOB_PER
Emotional Engagement	EE	Stress	SS
Rational Identification	RI	Working Environment	WE
Compatibility	CY	Workload	WD
Team Orientation	TN	Salary	SY
Motivation	MN		
Entrepreneurial Marketing	ENT_MAR		
Proactive Orientation	PO		
Opportunity Driven	OD		
Customer Intensity	CI		
Innovation Focused	IF		
Risk Management	RM		
Value Creation	VC		

Figure 5. A Model Modification showing Direct Causal Relationship of Employee Engagement, Entrepreneurial Marketing and Empowerment to Job Performance Considering Interrelationships of Other Variables

LEGEND

Employee Engagement	EMP_ENG	Employee Empowerment	EMP_EMP
Motivation	CY	Competencies	CS
Compatibility	MN	Self Determination	SD
Entrepreneurial Marketing	ENT_MAR	Impact	IS
Proactive Orientation	PO	Job Performance	JOB_PER
Opportunity Driven	OD	Stress Working	SS WE
Customer Intensity	CI	Environment	WD
Value Creation	VC	Workload	

1.8 Significance of the Study

The outcome of this analysis will be direct restaurant owners and managers some insights into engaging their employees to perform well in the entire business process. The findings can also assist the heads of human resources at restaurants in creating programs and events that adhered to the engagement and empowerment of the employees. The employee may also benefit from the outcome of this study because they can make it a basis for their decision while doing the day-to-day operation; likely impacting and contributing to the restaurant's overall performance as well as its profitability.

Such work would provide insights into the food industry at large in terms of social importance. Competitive advantage can be outsourced internally with restaurant employees who are committed, motivated and well-performed, as this can be a good tool in the food industry to combat rigid competition. The result can be used to craft programs and organizational policies that can result in the country's economic growth and development. Ultimately, the data and information provide an idea as a guide for the upcoming researchers to perform similar or related studies. This is also a starting point for broadening the study scope.

1.9 Definition of Terms

To establish common frame of reference, the following terms pertinent to the study are defined:

Employee Empowerment. This applies to the ways in which organizations provide a certain degree of autonomy and control to their workers in their daily activities. These can include getting a voice in process

improvements, helping to develop and implement new programs and tactics, and managing smaller teams with less oversight from senior management.

Employee Engagement. This refers to a workplace strategy that result in the right conditions for all members of a company to give every day their best, committed to the goals and values of their company, inspired to contribute to organizational progress, with an improved sense of their own well-being.

Entrepreneurial Marketing. This refers to the combination of two discrete areas of management. Entrepreneurship and marketing have arisen as distinct fields to explore the various aspects of marketing that are still not clarified by current mainstream marketing theories and concepts. Definitions of marketing and entrepreneurship vary widely so we can't expect a common concept of entrepreneurial marketing to encompass all.

Job Performance. This concerns how individuals perform their duties at work. In addition to preparation and natural ability (such as agility or an innate skill with numbers), job performance is influenced by factors in the workplace environment, including physically demanding activities, morale of workers, stress levels and prolonged working hours.

II. Method

Presented in this chapter are the research procedures employed in this study. This covers research design, location of analysis, population and sample, testing instruments, data collection and statistical methods used to achieve the anticipated results of this study.

2.1 Research Design

This study employed a quantitative research design utilizing the descriptive-correlation technique and structural equation model to generate the best-fit-model. Descriptive-correlation research design was applied to explain the subject phenomenon and to articulate what variables, conditions and attributes were present (Bordens & Abbott, 2002). In addition, this type of research is concerned with how or what happens in relation to some prior occurrence which has influenced or affected a present condition or event (Appleton, Christenson & Furlong, 2008). Specifically, this study utilized a correlational research approach since the study seeks to establish the relationship of employee engagement, entrepreneurial marketing and employee engagement that influence job performance among restaurant employees in Davao Region.

A structural model was utilized in the generation of the best fit model. Structural Equation Modeling is a technique that is especially useful in research that uses a variety of indicators (observed variables) to calculate latent variables –constructs (Chin, 1998) and theoretically evaluate relationships between latent variables (Hair, Sarstedt, Ringle, & Mena, 2012). The relationship assessment between the latent variables (inner model) is based on the quantitative level (outer or measurement model) evaluation of latent variables according to Hairet al. (2012). In this study, structural equation modeling is chosen as the researcher is interested in studying the theoretical constructs which are not observable.

Job performance is the endogenous variable in this research and could be called the 'latent' or 'unobservable' variable. Since latent variables are not measured directly, they cannot be tested directly. A hypothesized model created by AMOS version 22.0 for the research must be verified. Statistically, in an evaluation of the entire scheme of variables, the goal is to ascertain the degree to which the knowledge is compatible. If the model really fits, it discovers that the postulated relationships between the variables are plausible. Thus, if it is insufficient, the relationship's testability is rejected and a new model must be generated (Garrett, 2014). Many studies (Yilmaz, Ali & Flouris, 2015; Sing, Chakraborty & Roy, 2016; Jang, Zheng & Bosselman, 2017) used structural equation modelling to generate a model based on restaurant employees' job performance.

The research supports a realistic approach, as it uses simulation of structural equations (Rengiah & Sentosa, 2014). The realism paradigm allows for constructing theory and testing theories using in-depth surveys using multi-item test questions to determine latent job performance factors through the various exogenous variables, namely employee engagement, entrepreneurial marketing, and employee empowerment.

Structural equation modeling is the central statistical analytical technique used in this analysis to find out the factors affecting job performance among the job performance of the restaurant employees. Structural equation Modeling tests relationships between observed and latent variables by estimating multiple regression equations to check the model's overall fit (Henseler, Hubona & Ray, 2016).

Structural equation modeling (SEM) is the most suitable approach for this work compared to multivariate analysis procedures. Multivariate techniques are essentially descriptive in nature, such as general factor analysis, while structural equation modeling technique uses data to analyze inferential purposes, which a priori involves defining the pattern of intervariable relationships. Multiple regressions, factor analysis, multivariate variance analysis (MANOVA), have the same limitations; each technique can analyze one relationship at a time only. SEM is a multivariate methodology incorporating the aspects of multiple regression analysis (examining dependent relationships) and factor analysis (representing unmeasured definitions with multiple variables) to estimate a set of interrelated relationships of dependency (Hair et al., 2012). The methodology of SEM takes the confirmatory (hypothesis-testing) approach to

evaluate an impact on some phenomenon of structural theory. This structural theory is ideal for causal processes in which several variables are found (Bentler, 1988; Byrne, 2013).

SEM enables the researcher to determine the systemic and spontaneous measurement error effects (Bagozzi & Yi, 2012). It is possible to skew the parameter estimates from bivariate, multiple regressions and those from simultaneous equations where it is assumed that the observed variables are determined without error. According to Bagozzi, (2011), the calculation of parameters in models where there is a measurement error but not defined explicitly did not provide reliable estimates. Models of structural equation can be obtained by partitioning variance of errors and errors of structural prediction from the stated variance. The point is that traditional methods of data analysis are used on observable measurements only, and SEM procedures include both observed and non-observed (latent) variables.

The concept "Structural Equation Modeling" conveys two aspects of procedures; the causal processes under analysis are represented by a sequence of structural (i.e. regression) equations, and the structural relationships can be pictorially modelled to obtain a clearer conceptualization of the theory being studied. The hypothesized model could then be statistically evaluated in an analysis of the entire system of variables to determine to what degree it conforms to the results.

Based on these premise, if the model fits properly, postulated factor-to-factor relationships are considered reasonable when insufficient, then the relationship's testability is rejected (Shanmugam & Marsh, 2015). The features of the SEM model are estimation of various and interrelated interactions of reliance; the capacity to represent unattended ideas in those interactions and account for the measurement error in the assessment method; and the definition of a model to explain the whole set of interactions (Hair et al., 2012).

In this study, the Structural Equation models are schematically depicted with four geometric symbol settings- a circle or ellipse, a single-headed arrow, a triangle and a double-headed arrow. The circles or ellipse represent non-observed latent variables, rectangles represent observed variables, single headed arrows (almost) represent the effect of one variable on another, and double headed arrows (almost) represent co-variances or correlations among pairs of variables. The error terms (e) specific factors to a variable in the hypothesized model reflect residual variation within variables that did not account for the path ways. Measurement error is connected to a variable and residual error which predicts a non-observed variable (Cui, Groot, Schauer & Heskes, 2018).

2.2 Research Locale

The Philippines food service industry is composed of all forms of food retail including fast-food chains, food kiosk, cafes, bars, take-out, delivery stores and full service restaurants. The focus of this study are the full service restaurants limited to fastfood, fast casual and family style restaurants in the Davao Region who are already operating for five (5) years in the industry with at least 10 employees working in the different departments. For its tempo, convenience, and cheap prices, fast food restaurants are typically chains that attracted customers. Fast casual restaurant is a mash-up of fast food and casual dining, and is considered as one of the largest restaurant industry segments. The restaurant in the family style is somewhat similar to casual dining, with the exception that the food is served in larger dishes on tables where customers can eat the food and pass it on to other people at the table.

Davao Region is situated in the southeast part of Mindanao Island surrounding the Davao Sea. It is bounded by Surigao del Sur, Agusan del Sur and Bukidnon Provinces on the north. It is bounded by the Philippine Sea in the east, and by the provinces of Central Mindanao in the west. The Davao region faces Micronesia in the Southern Pacific Ocean to the east and Eastern Indonesia via the Celebes Sea to the south within the wider geographical sense. Davao Region is known as the centre for trade and investment in Mindanao, being home to several multinational companies that have chosen to set up their hubs and branches in the island region. See the subsequent page for the geographical location of the study.

Figure 6. Geographical Location of the Study

2.3 Population and Sample

In choosing the respondents, scientific process and purposive sampling were followed. The researcher opted to focus on micro, small and medium enterprise SME's as they have a significant role to play in the economy (Smit & Watkins, 2012). Section 3 of Republic Act No. 6967 known as the Magna Carta for Small Enterprise defined any business activity engaged in industry and services in a form of single proprietorship, cooperative, partnership or corporation whose total assets ranging from ; medium Php.15, 000,001 to Php.60, 000,000, small Php.1, 500,000 – Php.15, 000,000 and less than Php.1,500,001 respectively are considered micro enterprise.

A minimum of 403 employees from different full-service restaurant located in Davao Region were surveyed. The frontline staffs like the food attendants, busser, runner and bartender were technical education and skills development authority (TESDA) certified. However, some employees assigned in the administrative, logistics and back office do not have the same certification except the kitchen personnel like chef, prep and line cook were TESDA certified. The said restaurants must at least five years in the industry with minimum of 10 employees. These employees must have been in the company for at least one year who were assigned in operation, logistics, marketing and employees with administrative functions like in the human resource, finance and accounting in order to qualify. Structural Equation Model (SEM) is reliable to have a sample of 200 or above (Bagozzi & Yi, 2012). Moreover, SEM deals with large sample to be more effective and to reduce measurement errors (Hair et al., 2012). Thus, securing a sample of 403 is justified and appropriate. On the other hand, restaurants that are under franchising managed by a franchisee are excluded. The same with employees who are part-time and those who are employed in the company for less than one year are excluded as they cannot truly assess the employee job performance because of the nature, tenure and experience at work.

The participants of this research had the rights to discontinue answering the questionnaire regardless of the reason without negatively impacting their involvement and relationships with the research and the researcher. There were no pressure to those who choose to withdraw their participation to answer the questionnaire and explanations were also not required. The accurate sample size of the respondents was determined using the Slovin's formula. The said formula was computed after the researcher determined the actual population size of employees among restaurants in Davao Region. The data gathering took place on the fourth quarter of 2019.

2.4 Research Instrument

Primary data was collected using an adopted survey instrument. The instrument had four parts that generated information about the different variables considered in the study. These parts include the employee engagement, entrepreneurial marketing, employee empowerment and job performance.

The different components of the instrument were adopted from various related studies. They were restructured and modified based on the suggestions of the expert validators. After the validation, a pilot test was conducted and

Structural Equation Model of Job Performance among Restaurant Employees in Davao Region

Cronbach alpha was utilized to measure its validity. Cronbach's alpha is a measure of reliability correlated with variance that is compensated for by the underlying model's true score. The conceptual variable Model is being evaluated and calculated (Gupta, Swanson & Cunningham, 2010).

The survey on employee engagement was adopted from Kirsch (2016). The instrument was designed to measure the employee engagement as perceived by restaurant employees based on five factors, namely: emotional engagement, rational identification, compatibility, team orientation and motivation.

Range of Means	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very High	This means that the specific employee engagement is always manifested.
3.40 - 4.19	High	This means that the specific employee engagement is oftentimes manifested.
2.60 - 3.39	Moderate	This means that the specific employee engagement is sometimes manifested.
1.80 - 2.59	Low	This means that the specific employee engagement is rarely manifested.
1.00 - 1.79	Very Low	This means that the specific employee engagement is always manifested.

The survey on entrepreneurial marketing was lifted from the study of Fiore et al. (2013). The instrument was designed to measure the entrepreneurial marketing as perceived by restaurant employees based on four factors, namely: proactive orientation, opportunity driven, risk management and value creation.

Range of Means	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very High	This means that the specific entrepreneurial marketing is always manifested.
3.40 - 4.19	High	This means that the specific entrepreneurial marketing is oftentimes manifested.
2.60 - 3.39	Moderate	This means that the specific entrepreneurial marketing is sometimes manifested.
1.80 - 2.59	Low	This means that the specific entrepreneurial marketing is rarely manifested.

1.00 - 1.79	Very Low	This means that the specific entrepreneurial marketing is never manifested.
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The survey on employee empowerment was patterned from the study of Ugboro (2006). The instrument was designed to measure the employee empowerment as perceived by restaurant employees based on four factors, namely: meaningfulness, competence, self-determination and impact.

Range of Means	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very High	This means that the specific employee empowerment is always manifested.
3.40 - 4.19	High	This means that the specific employee empowerment is oftentimes manifested.
2.60 - 3.39	Moderate	This means that the specific employee empowerment is sometimes manifested.
1.80 - 2.59	Low	This means that the specific employee empowerment is rarely manifested.
1.0- 1.79	Very Low	This means that the specific employee empowerment is never manifested.

The survey on job performance was adopted from the study of Munisamy (2013). The instrument was designed to measure the job performance as perceived by restaurant employees based on four factors, namely: stress, working environment, workload and salary.

Range of Means	Descriptive Level	Interpretations
4.20 - 5.00	Very High	This means that the specific job performance is always manifested.
3.40 - 4.19	High	This means that the specific job performance is oftentimes manifested.
2.60 - 3.39	Moderate	This means that the specific job performance is sometimes manifested.
1.80 - 2.59	Low	This means that the specific job performance is rarely manifested.
1.00 - 1.79	Very Low	This means that the specific job performance is never manifested.

2.5 Data Collection

In gathering the needed information, the researcher was first secures consent to conduct the study from the university particularly from the University of Mindanao Ethics Review Committee. Letters were sent to the different restaurants in Davao Region to gain endorsement for the conduct of the survey. The researcher reproduced the needed number of questionnaires required. To facilitate the collection of the data, a timetable was set to give ample time to distribute and retrieve the survey instruments.

The retrieval of the instrument, encoding, and tabulation were done gradually. The numbers of instruments released and retrieved were carefully documented to aid the researcher in facilitating collection of needed data and were diligently encoded and tabulated. Results were subjected to statistical treatment, interpreted and presented based on the objective of the study following the order of the statements of the problem. With the results, conclusions were drawn and recommendations were formulated.

2.6 Statistical Tools

The researcher used the following statistical tools for the analysis of the data:

Mean. This was used to measure the level of employee engagement, entrepreneurial marketing, employee empowerment and job performance among restaurant employees.

Pearson Product Moment Correlation (Pearson R). This was utilized to find out the interrelationships between employee engagement, entrepreneurial marketing and employee empowerment to job performance.

Structural Equation Modelling. This was used to assess the interrelationships among the hypothesized models and as also with the determination of the best-fit-model of job performance among restaurant employees.

In evaluating the goodness of fit of the models, the following indices were computed and should meet the criteria: CMIN/DF should be $0 < < 2$ with a p-value > 0.05 , Tucker-Lewis should be > 0.9 , Comparative Fit Index (CFI) should be > 0.9 , Goodness of Fit Index (GFI) should be > 0.9 , Normative Fit Index (NFI) should be > 0.9 and root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA) should be < 0.05 and P of close Fit (PCLOSE) should be > 0.50 .

2.7 Ethical Consideration

The researcher would observe, ensure and adhere to full ethical standards in conducting the study. Before floating of questionnaire, the researcher would subject chapters one and two for review and approval by the University of Mindanao Ethics Review Committee (UMERC) and follow assessments of the research protocol and standardized requirements, in particular for population management and data such as, but not limited to: *voluntary participation*, respondents were granted the free will to participate without any sort of penalty or consequence. During the research process, respondents were not forced to contribute their time and effort. They were provided with complete knowledge of the procedure, goals and advantages of the study's behavior, and for whatever reason there were no rejection on the respondents' side.

Privacy and confidentiality were ensured in order that the respondents' personal and private information required and needed in the conduct of the study were all kept in private and with utmost confidentiality. As to *informed consent process*, the respondents of the study were asked to participate by obtaining consent which is a fundamental mechanism to ensure that respect was afforded to individuals by providing thoughtful consent for a voluntary act.

In the same manner, the research questionnaires were administered with the permission and approval from the authorized command channels. In the conduct of *recruitment*, only the appropriate respondents were allowed to participate in the study. The letters to conduct the said study were signed and monitored from the office of Professional School of the University of Mindanao which presented to the restaurant managers. It would be solely the discretion of the managers to allow the researcher to conduct the survey. Once approved, there were closed door meetings for a brief presentation of the study. Strictly only qualified employees who are employed in the company were the subject of the study because of the nature, tenure and experience at work and scope set by the researcher.

On managing respondent's *risk*, the study was only concentrate on determining the job performance among restaurant employees. Should there be an instance that the respondents were hesitant to participate and answer questions during the course of survey, respondents were be given the decision to answer the questions or not and they were also given the freewill to withdraw if they decide. Hence, there were no possible discomforts that a respondent may encounter during the survey/interview. As to how the respondents can *benefit*, the study greatly contributes to the understanding on dimensions that influence job performance among restaurant employees. Also, the result of this study guides them and gives some insights about then benefits of being engaged at work, to be entrepreneurially inclined and empowered in performing the task.

The researcher of this study would observe scholarly work as a reason for subjecting the research to *plagiarism* protocols. In addition, the researcher guarantees that there is no shred of evidence that someone else's work is misrepresented as his own. Proper recognition and attribution were given to all work contributors to prevent plagiarism or irregularity charges. To make this certain, the use of Turnitin software and/ or plagiarism detector was employed with diligence and avoidance of *fabrication* and *falsification*, the results of the study were presented in a manner which removes its findings from context, deceives readers, exaggerates claims or focuses on smaller sections of the observation without putting them into perspective.

Similarly, there was no trace of *conflict of interest* evident in this study. Affiliations with research sponsors including direct and indirect financial support as well as conflicts of interest were all be disclosed in order to establish transparency. In order to free from any ethical circumventions such as *deceit*, any falsehood about the author's identity and the nature and true purpose of the study were be avoided thus, this research did not make any forms of deception. Full *disclosure* of all elements relevant to respondents' participation were be exercised. This is to avoid misdirection or false information about some aspects of the research, whether in the procedures or the purpose.

As to *permission from organization/ location* in the conduct of the study, getting written permission from the restaurant owners and managers were undertaken and that has the authority to give permission for the conduct of the survey. Thus, a formal letter endorsed by the research adviser and the Dean was be sent to each identified restaurants before the actual survey was administered. The researcher was arrange a time convenient for the participants and in which did not disrupt working hours.

Lastly, the *authorship* of this research endeavour were accurately reflected the individual's contributions to the work and its reporting. Furthermore, the conduct of this study is designed and contributed to the growing body of knowledge and business literatures. The data that was gathered were carefully analysed by the researcher with the help of certified statistician. The progress of the study was monitored and commented by the adviser and to be approved by different experts. Hence, the author was explicitly signifies sufficient participation in the study and takes full responsibility and accountability of its content.

III. Result

Presented in this chapter are the data and deconstruction of findings based on the responses of the respondents of job performance among restaurant employees in Davao region. The discussion are sequence according to the following sub-headings: first is the level of employee engagement, entrepreneurial marketing, employee empowerment and job performance; second is the relationship between employee engagement and job performance, entrepreneurial marketing and job performance, employee empowerment and job performance; and the last is the best fit model that predicts job performance among restaurant employees in Davao region. It can be gathered from the data that standard deviation is below 1.00 that shows the consistency of the responses (Catapano, Graham, De Backer, Wiklund, Chapman, Drexel & Reiner, 2016).

3.1 Level of Employee Engagement among Restaurant Employees in Davao Region

In the Table 1 it showed the level of employee engagement among restaurant employees in Davao region. The overall mean score obtained on employee engagement is 4.37 with a standard deviation of 0.47 with a descriptive level of very high. This means the employee engagement is always manifested among restaurant employees in Davao region. The following mean rating of other indicators in employee engagement with the same descriptive level of very high are: emotional engagement obtained a mean rating of 4.23; rational identification attained 4.43 mean rating; compatibility

garnered a mean rating of 4.25; team orientation earned 4.38 mean score; and motivation acquired 4.55 mean score. The highest contributory indicator is motivation that rounded up with a mean rating of 4.55 and a descriptive level of very high that means it is an important factor under employee engagement as perceived by restaurant employees in the said region. Table 1 presents the summary of the level of employee engagement among restaurant employees in Davao region.

Table 1

Level of Employee Engagement of Restaurant Employees

Indicator	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Emotional Engagement	0.64	4.23	Very high
Rational Identification	0.63	4.43	Very high
Compatibility	0.68	4.25	Very high
Team Orientation	0.56	4.38	Very high
Motivation	0.56	4.55	Very high
Overall	0.47	4.37	Very high

3.2 Level of Entrepreneurial Marketing among Restaurant Employees in Davao region

Depicted in Table 2 is the summary of the level of entrepreneurial marketing among restaurant employees in Davao region. The overall mean score is 4.27 with the standard deviation of 0.57 with a descriptive level of very high that denotes that entrepreneurial marketing is always manifested by the respondents.

The mean rating of the indicators of entrepreneurial marketing are disclosed as follows: proactive orientation landed a mean rating of 4.18 with a descriptive level of high ; opportunity driven acquired 4.14 denotes a high descriptive level ; customer intensity amassed a mean rating of 4.35 with a very high descriptive level ; innovation focused garnered 4.38 mean score that indicates a very high descriptive level ; risk management attained 4.18 mean score and a high descriptive level and ; value creation reached a mean rating of 4.42 that designates a descriptive level of very high which also accomplished the highest contributory factor that means it is an important indicator in entrepreneurial marketing.

Table 2

Level of Entrepreneurial Marketing of Restaurant Employees

Indicator	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Proactive Orientation	0.75	4.18	High
Opportunity Driven	0.74	4.14	High
Customer Intensity	0.71	4.35	Very high
Innovation Focused	0.71	4.38	Very high
Risk Management	0.78	4.18	High
Value Creation	0.69	4.42	Very high
Overall	0.57	4.27	Very high

3.3 Level of Employee Empowerment among Restaurant Employees in Davao Region

Presented in table 3 is the level of employee empowerment among restaurant employees in Davao region. The overall mean rating is 4.47 and has a standard deviation of 0.53 with a descriptive level of very high that means it is always manifested by the respondents.

The mean score of the indicators of employee empowerment are revealed as follows: meaningfulness earned a means score of 4.71; competencies garnered a mean rating of 4.52; self-determination acquired 4.30 ; and impact achieved 4.30 mean score and all with a descriptive level of very high. Hence, it is always manifested. The highest contributory factor among is meaningfulness with 4.71 mean score. This connotes that meaningfulness is an important dimension in employee empowerment as perceived by restaurant employees. See table 3 below for the summary.

Table 3

Level of Employee Empowerment of Restaurant Employees

Indicator	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Meaningfulness	0.53	4.71	Very high
Competencies	0.60	4.52	Very high
Self-determination	0.74	4.35	Very high
Impact	0.77	4.30	Very high
Overall	0.53	4.47	Very high

3.4 Level of Job Performance among Restaurant Employees in Davao Region.

Presented below is the level of job performance among restaurant employees in Davao region. The overall mean score is 4.39 with a standard deviation of 0.73 with a descriptive level of very high that connotes that job performance is always manifested among the respondents.

The mean rating of the indicators of job performance are declared as follows: stress obtained 4.53 mean score ; working environment has a mean rating of 4.36 ; workload attained 4.28 means score and salary garnered 4.28 mean score all with the descriptive level of very high as perceived by restaurant employees. Stress has the highest contributory factor in job performance with a mean rating of 4.53. See the table below.

Table 4

Level of Job Performance of Restaurant Employees

Indicator	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Stress	0.48	4.53	Very high
Working Environment	0.59	4.36	Very high
Workload	0.59	4.38	Very high
Salary	0.74	4.28	Very high
Overall	0.50	4.39	Very high

3.5 Correlation between Employee Engagement and Job Performance

Table 5 displays the data on the results of correlations between employee engagement and job performance. The overall r-value attained by the aforesaid measure is .657 with a p-value less than 0.05 denotes a significant correlation to job performance thus,

rejecting the null hypothesis of no significant relationship.

Furthermore, it was observed that stress, working environment, workload and salary as indicators of job performance when correlated to emotional engagement, the overall r-value is 0.514 with $p < 0.05$ constitute significant relationship. Subsequently when indicators of job performance are correlated to rational identification the overall r-value is 0.516 with $p < 0.05$ hence significant. When the indicators of job performance were correlated to compatibility the overall r-value is 0.525 with $p < 0.05$ hence significant. Successively when the indicators of job performance were correlated to team orientation the overall r-value is 0.515 with $p < 0.05$ hence significant. Lastly, when the indicators of job performance were correlated to motivation the overall r-value is 0.498 with $p < 0.05$ hence significant it constitute a significant relationship. See table below for the summary of relationship between employee engagement and job performance. See the succeeding page.

Table 5

Significance on the Relationship between Employee Engagement and Job Performance of Restaurant Employees

Employee Engagement	Job Performance				
	Stress	Working Environment	Workload	Salary	Overall
Emotional Engagement	.366**	.459*	.418**	.455**	.514**
Rational Identity	.430**	.445*	.447**	.406**	.516**
Compatibility	.446**	.469*	.447**	.401**	.525**
Team Orientation	.419**	.433*	.495**	.381**	.515**
Motivation	.457**	.461*	.460**	.318**	.498**
Overall	.540**	.579*	.578**	.504**	.657**

3.6 Correlation between Entrepreneurial Marketing and Job Performance

Table 6 exhibits the data on the results of correlation between employee engagement and job performance. The overall r-value obtained from the said

measure is 0.604 with p-value of less than 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the result is significantly correlated with the null hypothesis being rejected.

Moreover, it was observed that stress, working environment, workload and salary as indicators of job performance when correlated to proactive orientation, the overall r-value is 0.484 with $p < 0.05$ hence, significant. When the indicators of job performance are correlated to opportunity driven, the overall r-value is 0.445 with $p < 0.05$ hence, significant. The same is true when indicators of job performance were correlated to customer intensity, innovation focused; risk management and value creation with the overall r-value is 0.494, .0520, 0.406 and 0.493 respectively with p-value below 0.05 hence, significant. See table for a detailed significance level of entrepreneurial marketing and job performance. See the next page.

Table 6

Significance on the Relationship between Entrepreneurial Marketing and Job Performance of Restaurant Employees

Entrepreneurial Marketing	Job Performance				
	Stress	Working Environment	Workload	Salary	Overall
Proactive Orientation	.366**	.404*	.439**	.400**	.484**
Opportunity Driven	.324**	.393*	.396**	.366**	.445**
Customer Intensity	.444**	.417*	.469**	.341**	.494**
Innovation Focused	.459**	.442*	.504**	.352**	.520**
Risk Management	.347**	.288*	.359**	.357**	.406**
Value Creation	.397**	.415*	.442**	.393**	.493**
Overall	.496**	.501*	.554**	.471**	.604**

3.7 Correlation between Employee Empowerment and Job Performance

As illustrated on Table 7 the data on the results of correlations between employee empowerment and job performance. The overall r-value attained by the aforesaid measure is 0.644 with a p-value less than 0.05 meaning it is highly correlated to job performance thus, rejecting the null hypothesis of no significant relationship.

In addition, it was observed that stress, working environment, workload and salary as indicators of job performance when correlated to meaningfulness, the overall r-value is 0.547 with $p < 0.05$ hence, significant. Likewise, when indicators of job performance were correlated to competence, the overall r-value is 0.469 with $p < 0.05$ hence, significant. Similarly, when the indicators of job performance were correlated to self-determination, the overall r-value is 0.501 with $p < 0.05$ hence, significant. Lastly, when the indicators of job performance were correlated to impact the overall r-value is 0.540 with $p < 0.05$ hence, significant. The probability values showed significant correlations. Next page shows the summary of significance relationship of employee empowerment to its endogenous variable job performance.

Table 7

Significance on the Relationship between Employee Empowerment and Job Performance of Restaurant Employees

Employee Empowerment	Job Performance				
	Stress	Working Environment	Workload	Salary	Overall
Meaningfulness	.534**	.468**	.495**	.365**	.547**
Competence	.440**	.417**	.449**	.293**	.469**
Self-determination	.402**	.452**	.492**	.342**	.501**
Impact	.448**	.456**	.490**	.415**	.540**
Overall	.564**	.562**	.605**	.447**	.644**

3.8 Best Fit Model of Job Performance

In terms of the research question associated to the model that best represents the best variable that predicts job performance, the original proposed model outlined in Figure 1-5 requires some modification in order to fit the data. There were five generated models presented in this study. The summary of the findings of the goodness of fit measures of these five generated models is presented in Table 8.

Table 8

Summary of Goodness of Fit Measures of the Five Generated Models

Model	P-value (>0.05)	CMIN/DF (0<value<2)	GFI (>0.95)	CFI (>0.95)	NFI (>0.95)	TLI (>0.95)	RMSEA (<0.05)	P-close (>0.05)
1	.000	5.524	.810	.830	.802	.805	.107	.000
2	.000	4.113	.857	.885	.854	.866	.089	.000
3	.000	3.458	.921	.941	.919	.925	.079	.000
4	.000	2.644	.922	.654	.928	.944	.065	.000
5	.088	1.307	.978	.994	.976	.991	.028	.976

Legend:

- CMIN/DF - Chi Square/Degrees of Freedom
- NFI - Normed Fit Index
- GFI - Goodness of Fit Index
- TLI - Tucker-Lewis Index
- RMSEA - Root Mean Square of Error Approximation
- CFI - Comparative Fit Index

All the indices included must continuously fall within acceptable ranges when identifying the best fit model. The value of the chi-square / degrees of liberty should be between 0 and 2, with the corresponding p-value of 0.05 or higher. Root Mean Square of Error Approximation must be less than 0.05 and must be higher than or equal to 0.05 for its respective Pclose value. Other indexes such as the Normed Fit Index, the Tucker-Lewis Index, the Comparative Index and the Fit Index Goodness must all be higher than 0.95.

The first generated structural were EMP_ENG, ENT_MAR, EMP_EMP and JOB_PER. The said model displays the direct effect of the exogenous variables:

employee engagement, entrepreneurial marketing and employee empowerment towards job performance. All indices did not reach the acceptable criteria, hence, a constructed poor fit model. The model is appended in this study as Figure A-1.

The second model includes the interrelationship among employee engagement, entrepreneurial marketing and employee empowerment towards job performance. The model was found a poor fit as presented by the CMIN/DF= 4.113 with its p-value=.000 and RAMSEA =.089 with Pclose=.000 as it did not reach the criteria and hence indicate a poor fit. The model is appended in this study as Figure A-2.

The third structural model considers the correlation of employee engagement, employee empowerment and the direct causal effect towards job performance. But, the model was still found non-fitting to the data as indicated by CMIN/DF=3.458, p-value=.000 and RMSEA=.079 with Pclose=.000. The model is appended in this study as Figure A-3.

The fourth structural model shows relationship between employee engagement and entrepreneurial marketing and their causal relationship to job performance. Model 4 was found still to have indices that indicate a poor fit as indicated specifically CMIN/DF=2.644, p-value=0.000 and RMSEA=.065 with pclose=0.000. The model is appended in this study as Figure A-4.

Finally, the fifth structural model is a model modification of EMP_ENG, ENT_MAR, EMP_EMP, and JOB_PER. The Goodness of Fit Measures of Structural Model 5 presented in Figure 7 depicts a network of interrelationships of exogenous variables to job performance as the endogenous variable considering the interrelationship of other variables present. As displayed in Table 8, the goodness of fit of Model 5 was examined using the following indices: Chi-square/Degree of Freedom (CMIN/DF), Root Mean Square of Error Approximation (RMSEA), Normed Fit Index (NFI), Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI), Comparative Fit Index (CFI)/Goodness of Fit Index (GFI).

The criterion for each index indicating a good fit for all outcomes must be in accordance with the requirements shown in Table 8. The results as reflected by CMIN/DF= 1.307, p-value =.088, NFI = .976, TLI = .991, CFI = .994, GFI = .978, RMSEA = .028 and Pclose = .976, fall within the indices thus the result signify the best fit model. Figure 7 shows the structural model 5 generated, of which the direct link between the latent exogenous variables and their direct effect on the latent endogenous variable. The endogenous latent variable is Job Performance (JOB_PER) with observed variables namely Stress (SS), Working Environment (WE) and Workload (WD).

All exogenous latent variables are still present in the modified model and these are the following: Employee Engagement (EMP_ENG) with two remained observed variables the Compatibility (CY) and Motivation (MIN), Entrepreneurial Marketing (ENT_MAR) which is measured by Proactive Orientation (PO), Opportunity Driven (OD), Customer Intensity (CI) and Value Creation (VC) and Employee Empowerment

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(EMP_EMP) which is measured by Competencies (CS), Self Determination (SD) and Impact (IS).

To sum it up, the generated model 5 followed on this page clearly illustrates the importance of employee engagement, entrepreneurial marketing and employee empowerment as the major predictors of job performance among restaurant employees in Davao Region. These variables play a foremost role for restaurant employees to continuously improve their job performance in the firm where they belong. Thus, results were supported on detailed on the next chapter.

Figure 7: Structural Model 5 in Standardized Solution

Legend:

		ENT_MAR	Entrepreneurial Marketing
EMP_ENG	Employee Engagement	PO	Proactive Orientation
CY	Compatibility	OD	Opportunity Driven
MN	Motivation	CI	Customer Intensity
		VC	Value Creation
JOB_PER	Job Performance		
SS	Stress	EMP_EMP	Employee Empowerment
WE	Working Environment		
WD	Workload	CS	Competencies
		SD	Self determination
		IS	Impact

Estimates of Variable Regression Weights in Best Fit Model

			Estimate	S.E	Beta	C.R.	P-value
emp_emp	<-	emp_eng	1.136	.160	.696	7.111	***
ent_mar	<-	emp_eng	1.052	.193	.743	5.448	***
ent_mar	<-	emp_em	.077	.096	.089	.803	.422
job_per	<-	emp_em	.163	.066	.254	2.454	.014
job_per	<-	emp_eng	.706	.128	.675	5.516	***
MN	<-	emp_eng	1.000		.651		
CY	<-	emp_eng	1.155	.109	.662	10.599	***
VC	<-	ent_mar	1.000		.738		
CI	<-	ent_mar	1.039	.068	.748	15.219	***
OD	<-	ent_mar	1.036	.091	.713	11.393	***
PO	<-	ent_mar	1.014	.091	.693	11.111	***
IS	<-	emp_em	1.000		.770		
SD	<-	emp_em	.971	.078	.774	12.504	***
CS	<-	emp_em	.774	.076	.756	10.133	***
SS	<-	job_per	1.000		.786		
WE	<-	job_per	1.265	.084	.811	15.077	***
WD	<-	job_per	1.316	.085	.843	15.507	***

Legend:

CY - Compatibility	VC - Value Creation	emp_emp - Employee Empowerment
MN - Motivation	ent_mar - Entrepreneurial Marketing	SS - Stress
emp_eng - Employee Engagement	CS - Competencies	WE - Working Environment
PO - Proactive Orientation	SD - Self Determination	WD - Workload
OD - Opportunity Driven	IS - Impact	job_per - Job Performance
CI - Customer Intensity		

IV. Discussion

Included in this chapter are the thorough discussions of the level of employee engagement, entrepreneurial marketing, employee empowerment and job performance. Also, discussed in this section are the correlations and significant influences between employee engagement, entrepreneurial marketing, and employee empowerment on job performance. Lastly, the best fit model that predicts job performance of restaurant employees in Davao Region.

4.1 Employee Engagement

The overall outcome of the employee engagement was taken from the result of the ratings of the respondents on the variable's measurement construct such as emotional engagement, rational identification, compatibility, team orientation and motivation were all rated as very high. Thus, this simply indicates that the respondents evaluated employee engagement with all variable measurement as always manifested.

The very satisfactory level of employee engagement in terms of emotional engagement denotes that employees feel emotionally attached to the strategic choices of the company. This is consonance with the study of Mani, (2011) and Sundaray, (2011) that employees engaged put all their energy and excitement into their work, and that they care about their organization's future. This clearly indicates that employees are deeply connected to their work and it shows that in some points as if the company's problems become employee's problem.

In terms of rational identification, employees have a clear understanding of their goals and objectives in completion to their daily task. This is valid as Mone and London (2014) added that employee engagement is about recognizing one's position in an organization as to where it suits the intent and objectives of the organizations. This apparent awareness justifies that employees are expected to complete their assignment and to outperform as they understand that their role is aligned to the business objective of the company.

In relation to compatibility about job fit, loyalty and commitment, employees believe that they owe something from the company and not thinking of leaving. This is supported by Orletsky (2015) stated that employees agree to give an organization his time and energy in exchange for financial compensation, professional development and the chance to fulfillment of his career ambition.

With regards to team orientation, the employees do everything they can to help colleagues who have heavy workload and they do their best to help improve team's performance. This is accompanied by the discretionary initiative that claims workers ability to go beyond the call of duty such as supporting others with heavy workloads, volunteering for additional duties and more, and looking for ways to more efficiently perform their jobs. Strom, Sears and Kelly (2014) affirmed that people encompasses the understanding that individual and departmental contribution benefit the larger enterprise.

Lastly, in terms of motivation, employees continue to build their skills to increase their value to the organization. Every type of employee has a sense of achievement and motivation to fulfill personal and professional goals (Gerhart & Fang, 2015). Motivated workers are thus motivated to put extra effort into helping the company succeed.

4.2 Entrepreneurial Marketing

The overall high level of the entrepreneurial marketing is the result of the ratings of the respondents on the variable's measurement namely customer-intensity, innovation-focused and value creation that all garnered a very high rating. Whereas, proactive-orientation, opportunity-driven and risk management gained a high rating that means respondents evaluated these measurement constructs as oftentimes manifested.

The very high level result of entrepreneurial marketing in terms of customer-intensity denotes that business marketing efforts is the reflection of knowledge of what the customers really want from its products and service. This is the reason why Centeno, Hart and Dinnie(2013) asserted that entrepreneurs need to be aware that business public's image may reflect consumer's perception of their firm. Hence, such business creates solid relationships with customers through its marketing efforts. Likewise, Sheth, Sisodia and Sharma,(2000) believed that successful business are those that place a greater emphasis on customer intensity. In terms of innovation-focused, entrepreneurs believe that communicating with customers is a great way to identify innovation opportunities. Furthermore, employees contribute a lot of ideas to innovation undertaken by business. This proves the proposition of York and Venkataraman, (2010) that day-to-day entrepreneurs are better at addressing environmental uncertainty and providing innovation. In terms of value creation, the business expects every employee to be looking for way to create more value for customers. As Gummerus, (2013) emphasized that creating value for customers have been a long goal of any marketing endeavour. Hence, value creation has a positive significant effect to business performance declared by Nuryakin, et al. (2018). There is no doubt why business continuously tries to find new ways to create value for the customer.

The respondents rated entrepreneurial marketing in terms of proactive-orientation as high or it means oftentimes manifested as the business is frequently one of the first in the community to alter its marketing methods. This is consonance with the study of Stenholm et al. (2016) who asserted that company adopted a strategic posture wherein risks are welcome, brand new products and services are explored while maintains a proactive local competition. Meanwhile, Barrales-Molina, Martinez-Lopez and Gazquez-Abad (2014) suggest that proactive market orientation is more of a marketing capability. In terms of opportunity-driven, when new market opportunity arises, the business enterprise is very quick to act on them. These business activities requires a mind-set of an entrepreneur declared by Ferm

(2018) and supported by the study of Kuratko and Audretsch (2013) who confirmed that entrepreneurial greatly involves opportunity seeking. Whereas, the concept of opportunity driven means that the market imperfection is waiting to be exploited which is also an opportunity for potential profit as stated by Holmes and Jorlov, (2015). In terms of risk-management, when a business enterprise decides to pursue a new marketing direction, it is done in stages rather than all at once to reduce the risk involved. This is supported by Bank and Brusbauer (2014) that enterprise has to pay attention to the aspect of managing to identify risk that could potentially cause the venture to fail. No doubt, for an enterprise to engage in marketing efforts at low cost to reduce risk associated with it. However, this does not contest not to take risk as Goffee and Scase (2015) described entrepreneurs who have been labelled as a risk taker.

4.3 Employee Empowerment

The overall very high level of the employee empowerment is the result of the ratings of the respondents on the variable's measurement namely meaningfulness, competence, self-determination and impact that all garnered a very high rating. This indicates that respondents evaluated employee empowerment with all variable measurement constructs as always manifested.

The very high level result of employee empowerment in terms of meaningfulness denotes that the work employees do is meaningful to them. This is parallel to the proposition of Fernandez and Moldogaziev (2013) who said that meaningfulness is the individual's intrinsic caring about a given task in relations to the individual's own value system. Thus, the work they do is important to them. In terms of competence the employees are confident of their ability to do their job. Backed by the analysis of Harrison and Waite (2015), who stressed that not only are capable people feeling skilled but they also feel confident and competent in their work. Thus, this gives self-assurance to employees about their capabilities to perform their daily work activities.

With regards to self-determination, employees have confidence that they can decide on their own as how to go about doing their work. As mentioned in (Jha, 2014), employees are given the opportunity to make decision in the workplace by increasing their decision-making autonomy. This means that employees possess considerable opportunity for independence and freedom however, within acceptable parameters or at least based on the standard protocol of the organization. When problem arise due to poor decision making, employees should at least be willing to take another lead by correcting the issues and concern. Based on these premise, Fatima, et al.(2013) suggested that this is simply breakdown of the traditional hierarchical structure.

With regards to impact employees feel that they have a great deal of influence over what is happening in their department. When individuals believe they can have an influence on the structure on which they are located, then they are successful (Rasouli et al.,2013). This reflects to the proposition of Luoh et al.(2014) that to what degree an individual can affect political, functional or operational outcomes at work.

4.4 Job Performance

The overall very high level of job performance is the result of the ratings of the respondents on the variable's measurement construct like stress, working environment, workload and salary that all incurred a very high rating. This indicates that the respondents evaluated their job performance always manifested and perceived.

The very high level of job performance in terms of stress denotes that employees tend to see problems as challenge rather than as obstacles. This is in line with the proposition of (Ekienabor, 2016) that described stress as a dynamic situation in which a person is confronted with opportunities, constraints or demands related to what he or she wants for which the result is perceived to be both uncertain and important. The World Health Organization (WHO) published by Semmer (2007), which describes workplace stress, further supports this notion by questioning people's ability to cope with job demands and stresses that are unrivaled in their skills and abilities. It means that stress at work is inevitable and part of employee's acceptance to work is the stressors accompanied to their role.

In terms of working environment employees understand the importance to value and respect their colleagues, they are rewarded for the quality of their efforts, they feel that the management appreciates their suggestion and leadership and they have the ability to solve problems immediately to satisfy their manager. This sum up to Spector (1997) as cited in Raziq and Maulabakhsh (2015), work environment is consist of workplace safety, job security, authorization in decision making, recognition and co-worker relationship. Thus, indicated by (Kaya, 2015) that work environment does not consist of physical items such as tools, devices, design but also in a form of psychosocial environment.

As far as workload is concerned, the organization is doing an outstanding job in keeping its workers updated about matters that affect them. This is done according to Feng and Cao (2017) heavy workload has been shown to have a negative impact on turnover. Thus, Suarathana and Riana (2016) and Qureshiet al. (2013) indicated managers would actively monitor employee workloads to minimize turnover on behalf of the businesses. This is an obvious fact that the workload is not overestimated and the firm's focus is to find win - win solutions to workplace problems.

In terms of salary, in which the respondents rated it as always manifested. This clearly indicates that employees are satisfied with financial growth in the company. This is true as (Karatepe, 2013) affirmed that the effective ways for motivating the employees or staffs in the restaurant industry are adequate compensation, recognition programs and financial rewards which are used by the HR management. The employees in this industry are well pampered in terms of benefits as they are provided with meals and accommodation. Not to mention the tips, overtime pay and product commission excluded from their fix salary. Therefore, these employees are rewarded for the quality of their efforts.

4.5 Correlation between Employee Engagement and Job Performance

The variable relationship test shows an important connection between employee engagement and job performance leading to the study's null hypothesis being rejected. This means that there is an association between engagement and job performance. The overall result of the employee's engagement of restaurant employees among Davao region is significantly correlated with job performance. Stress, working environment, workload and salary are associated with employee engagement in a unique state.

Employee engagement plays a significant role in job performance (Fernet et al., 2015). Engaged employees are viewed more productive almost every section in the workplace (Bakker & Albrecht, 2018). They are enthusiastic towards their work. They are expected to outperform, (Saks & Gruman, 2014). They think for their organization's future (Sundaray, 2011). Unengaged workers are likely to be underperforming (Saks & Gruman, 2014). On the other hand, engaged employees are well aware of the business climate and the work they do to boost their efficiency with the aid of their co-workers (Mani, 2011). The view suggests employee engagement has a clear understanding of the expectations, the goals for their work. The relation between the works they do and the overall strategy for the company is clear to them.

The JDR-WE model that supports the relationship of employee engagement and job performance by Schaufeli and Bakker,(2004) found that increasing the job opportunities resulted in higher work commitment and lower subsequent absenteeism. Supervisors and co-workers scored higher on in-role results than other highly engaged employees (Halbesleben & Wheeler, 2008). Emotional engagement also come from the feeling that work done matters and the co-workers are committed, passionate and motivated by the work they do in respect to company's mission (Schutte & Loi, 2014). If the employees are deeply connected to the company they make sure that they meet or excel on their job. Once employees make mistake, they take the accountability to correct what they have done.

Furthermore, employee engagement significantly affects not only productivity but also employee's retention, loyalty, customer satisfaction and overall stakeholder value (Sundaray, 2011). Work-unit level participation has resulted in increased innovativeness by higher personal initiative (Hakanen et al.,2008). In most situations, employees believe that they owe something to the company and they think that if moving out to the same industry is a great betrayal and a shameful act. The sample view indicates employee's loyalty and commitment towards the company.

4.6 Correlation between Entrepreneurial Marketing and Job Performance

The test of relationship between variables reveals a significant relationship between entrepreneurial marketing and job performance which leads to rejecting the null hypothesis of the study. This implies that entrepreneurial marketing is correlated with job performance. Further, it implies that entrepreneurial marketing has something to do with job performance. The overall result of the entrepreneurial marketing of restaurant employees among Davao region is significantly correlated with job performance. In singular state, stress, working environment, workload and salary are correlated to entrepreneurial marketing.

The relationship between entrepreneurial marketing and job performance has been evaluated to have significant relationship by Hills and Hultman, (2013). The study of Umeze and Ohen, (2015) found this variable to have significant manner to be linked to job performance. In established organization under food service industry, entrepreneurial activity leads to improved performance said by Lee, Kim,Seo and Hight (2015). A positive impact on firm's performance is attributed to entrepreneurial and market orientation (Long, 2013). This has been proven true by Jogaratnam, (2002) as he found out that entrepreneurial marketing has been identified as a method applied by small independent restaurant business.

Pro-activeness as one indicator of entrepreneurial marketing shows a strong relationship towards firm's performance indicated by Lumpkin and Dess,(2001). Whereas, innovativeness plays a critical element of the business performance stated by Cooper, (2000) further requires a mind-set of an entrepreneur agreeing to Fiore,et al.(2013).This summarizes that entrepreneurial marketing leads to better performance because it allows marketing to be managed not just innovatively and pro-actively hence, this opens marketing to new methods as explained by Hallback and Gabrielson, (2013). In fact, Armstrong and Baron (2005) said that controlling the output of workers promotes the successful execution of strategic and organizational objectives in which those elements are within the framework of the traditional marketing strategy model that is useful for increasing the competitiveness of a company.

4.7 Correlation between Employee Empowerment and Job Performance

The test of relationship between variables reveals a significant relationship between employee empowerment and job performance which leads to rejecting the null hypothesis of the study. This implies that employee empowerment is linked with job performance. Further, it implies that employee empowerment has something to do with job performance. The overall result of the employee empowerment among restaurant employees in Davao region is significantly correlated with job performance. In singular state, stress, working environment, workload and salary are correlated to employee empowerment.

The employee empowerment provides a direct relationship with job performance as Crant (2000)described motivation to be proactive in the sense of, dealing with employees who are highly performers, it is essential, and otherwise employee's performance declines. There is a positive relationship between human capital in a professional

organization in terms of intellectual capabilities, expertise, and social capital to the firm's success as stated by Hitt, Bierman, Shimizu, and Kochhar's (2001). Another study by Meyerson and Dewettinck (2012) which described employee empowerment is a motivational technique designed to improve performance if properly managed through increased levels of employee participation and self-determination.

The proposition of Hechanova et al.(2016) in which this relationship is anchored found that there was a positive correlation between psychological strength and job performance. Competence as postulated by some writers that this is the most important aspect of psychological strength because it is the feeling of self-efficacy that creates perseverance and strives to do the hard works (Wang & Zhang, 2013). In a systematic meta-analysis the perceived control relationship including engagement and autonomy with a variety of outcomes Goharet al.(2015) found clear evidence of positive job performance associations. This is when employees have enough independence and accountability towards their work as they allow employees to make decision such as the method of performing the job (GanjiNia et al.,2013) as to the manner of time , speed and right efforts towards their work (Wong et al., 2014).

4.8 The Best Fit Model that Predicts Employee's Job Performance

Figure 7 in chapter 3 shows the generated structural model 5. It depicts a network of interrelationships of exogenous variables toward endogenous variable. The exogenous variables are Employee Engagement (EMP_ENG) which is measured by Compatibility (CY) and Motivation (MN), Entrepreneurial Marketing (ENT_MAR) which is measured by Proactive Orientation (PO), Opportunity Driven (OD), Customer Intensity (CI) and Value Creation (VC) and the other one is Employee Empowerment (EMP_EMP) which is measured by Competencies (CS), Self Determination (SD) and Impact (IS). The endogenous variable uses Job Performance (JOB_PER) which is measured by namely Stress (SS), Working Environment (WE) and Workload (WD).

From the model it could be seen that only compatibility and motivation remained as a measurement construct of employee engagement. This supports the claim of (McCann, Sparks & Kohntopp, 2017), who expressed that hiring for compatibility starts with creating a healthy corporate culture that attracts compatible talent with high performance and puts in place processes to maintain and grow such talent. Hiring with compatibility in mind begins well before an applicant's first interview. Employees then need encouragement to feel good about their work and perform in an optimal way (Chen, Hsieh & Chem, 2014). Motivated workers are excited to perform their jobs and responsibilities to the best of their ability and as a consequence increase in production numbers (Ganta, 2014).

The model also shows the interrelationship of compatibility and motivation. This interconnectedness has been corroborated with the work of Semmer (2007) under the World Health Organization (WHO) which stated that occupational stress comes out when there is unmatched of knowledge and abilities. A highly motivated employees believe that they have the right skills and talents to perform their job and tries his best in carryout each and every aspect of his duties and responsibilities (Supaman, Nasir & Serif, 2019). The outcome from a motivated employee result to high level of productivity (Zameer, Ali, Nisar & Amir, 2014). Therefore, employees feel satisfied which resulted to lower absenteeism and reducing turn-over rate. Based on these premises, these employees are committed to their job and also a reflection of loyalty and trust to the company.

Proactive orientation, opportunity driven, customer intensity and value creation are variables left that belong to entrepreneurial marketing. It is noted that the innovative nature of proactive orientation as theorized by Lamoreetal.(2013) and strategic posture adopted by the company results to organizational success like the new market offers, overcoming the fear of risks and explore new products or services in the market while maintaining a proactive outlook as compared to its rivals in term of dealing with market opportunities (Stenholm, Pukkinen, & Heinonen, 2016).

Similarly opportunity-drivenness is predicated on the market imperfections waiting to be exploited for sustainable profit potential (Holmes & Jorlöv, 2015). A company that was set up to take advantage of a market opportunity is supposed to have a greater propensity to expand (Zall, Faghiih, Ghotbi, & Sahar, 2013). Entrepreneurial greatly involves opportunity seeking (Kuratko & Audretsch, 2013) and a firm's success can be attributed to a firm's ability to seek promising opportunity.

In line with this, customer intensity has been found to be the propensity of a business entrepreneur to create marketing relationships that answer individual customer needs, wishes, and expectations and relate more directly to customers (Fiore et al., 2013). As to value-creation, the main subject of entrepreneurial marketing (Gökbulut & Özdemir, 2013) that serve as goal of any marketing endeavor (Gummerus, 2013). Looking into its management importance it has been notes that the companies who were able to create value over extended period of time were able to successfully adapt and renew the models of their enterprise and further sustain their value creation (Achtenhagen, Melin & Naldi, 2013).

The model also shows the interrelationship of proactive orientation and opportunity driven. Another interrelationship of customer intensity and value creation emerged. This interconnectedness has been corroborated with Grinstein(2008) that proactive companies are opportunity driven as respond to market condition. Various authors have considered that that SME's by nature are customer oriented which is an essential resource to dive opportunity (Christensen, 2014). Forward looking companies foresee opportunities. The latter customer intensity interrelates value creation is supported by Wagner, Eggert and Lindemann (2010) that emphasized organization exist as value-oriented. Example shows how relational approach, which is an extension of product-based approach, confirms that interest is not constrained by the product but also embedded in buyer-seller relationships consisting of relationship practices, resource relationships and personal ties (Pels, Polese & Brodie , 2012).

Competencies, self-determination and impact have been proven as observed variables of employee empowerment. This concurs the study of Harrison and Waite, (2015); Lorinkova et al. (2013) found that not only capable people feel qualified, they also feel confident and competent. In addition, workers always feel personal competence and believe they learn and succeed if they are to face new challenges (Soltani & Sanatzadeh, 2013).

Self-determination is also an indicator of empowerment. This is about employee's responsibility and ownership towards their task (Rasouli et al., 2013). The feeling of freedom to make decisions about their job and have ample authority with respect to the direction, time and pace of their mission (Wong et al., 2014). Self-determination contributes to understanding, an engagement in action and hardship resilience Deci and Ryan (2014).

Finally, impact is a degree to which the individual can "influence political, administrative, or operational outcomes at work" (Men & Stacks, 2013). Recently (Boussalem, 2015) finds that the motive for impact can make it profitable for an employer to give employees autonomy in the choice of effort or task. Capable employees feel they can play an important role in achieving the organizational goals by meeting their responsibilities; they can monitor the job results and consequences, and they can have a positive impact on what happens, and they can manage the obstacles and barriers (Rezaei et al., 2012).

The model also shows the interrelationship of self-determination and impact. Another interrelationship of competence and impact depicted in the model. This interconnectedness has been emphasized by organizational scholars such as Graves and Luciano (2013) that self-determination impact employees performance at work. In line with this, employees need to believe that they can tackle obstacles, achieve outcomes, learn and grow, and adapt to change in order to feel psychologically competent (Graves & Luciano, 2013). Based on these, a self-determined employee positively impact employee's performance at work. On the other hand, the positive impact of employee in terms of duties and responsibilities in the organization is based on how good, competent and motivated he is at work (Azar & Shafiqhi, 2013). Based on these premise, employee's impact at work is very important aspect as it reflects employee's performance.

Stress, working environment and workload are variables left that belong to job performance. Scientifically defined stress as an individual's reaction to the outcomes of external environmental conditions that placed undue psychological, behavioral, and physiological pressure on that individual (Suharno & Despinur, 2017). Furthermore, employees are confronted with uncertainties, opportunities, constraints and demand related at work (Ekienabor, 2016). The strain when employees face a certain demand that does not conform to their expertise at the professional level creates or poses a challenge and threat to the employee's capabilities, which in turn would create a struggle for life in terms of being employed in a position as Sohail and Rehman (2015) created.

As far as the work environment is concerned, the willingness of workers to share knowledge with each other depends on how it is used by management based on Akinyele (2010) research. Organization must provide a healthy and positive work environment to ensure a positive working condition for employees to improve job satisfaction and guarantee a better work quality from employees (Ismael & Razak, 2016). Cited by Raziq and Maulabakhsh (2015), work environment consist of workplace safety, security of job, authorization in decision making, co-workers relationship, and recognition.

Based on these premises, the need of safety, security, recognition and autonomy have to be fulfilled in the workplace as this help to increase their job satisfaction that eventually improve their commitment and productivity (Salunke, 2015). On the other hand, workload refers to the amount of work that is allocated to an employee to do. The heavy workload may affect the physical or mental health, efficiency, or productivity of an employee. As a consequence, it has been shown that heavy workloads have a negative impact on productivity (Feng & Cao, 2017), certainly contribute to a stressful state and trigger pressure, injuries or illness. High turnover of staff brings with it the issues of both high labor costs and quality problems that harm a company's performance and development (Flook, Goldberg, Pinger, Bonus & Davidson 2013).

The model also shows the interrelationship of stress and work environment. Another variable shows interrelationship the work environment and workload. This interconnectedness has been corroborated by Mostert, Nell, Mostert and Rothmann (2008) that stress is an outcome of an individual due to working environment. It emphasized that for extended working hours while simultaneously meeting production target and deadlines have tendency towards a high level of stress (MacEachen, Polzer & Clarke, 2008). In perspective of Munir (2011), workload and time constraints were significant contributors to work stress and unhappy with current culture where employees are required to work longer hours and cope with large workload. Based on these premise, therefor work overload contributes stress, stress diminishes workload and a poor working environment possess high level of stress.

V. Conclusion

The following conclusions are taken in light of the research results. This study's results explicitly verify the best predictors of the job performance among employees. First, the findings exposed that in terms of employee's job performance, of the three exogenous variables, employee empowerment got the highest total mean. Therefore, it can be determined that employee empowerment is a precondition element to employees job performance. And among all observed variables meaningfulness obtained the highest-level mean score which is also a direct variable of employee empowerment. It implies that employee empowerment is constructive to the quality of job performance to employees in the company.

The results on the test of the null hypotheses stating that there is no significant relationship and influence between employee engagement, entrepreneurial marketing and employee empowerment to job performance were all

rejected. Thus, all those exogenous variables have significant relationship and influence on the endogenous variables. Therefore, result of the study corroborates with the propositions that there is a link between employee engagement and job performance (Fernet et al., 2015); there is an association between entrepreneurial marketing and job performance (Lee et al., 2013) and that there is a connection employee empowerment and job performance ((Agugustain et al., 2019). Moreover, the null hypothesis stating that there is no model that best fits to job performance among restaurant employees in Davao region was rejected.

5.1 Recommendation

The following recommendations are made in considerations of the results and conclusions of the study. The results concluded that entrepreneurial marketing has the low mean score. It is recommended that employees must have a real passion for continually changing the way product and services are being marketed. It would be best to tap all employees in most marketing efforts of the business specially that marketing department less exist in food service industry. Also, develop a chain of entrepreneurial mind-setting to employees by inculcating to them that the business does not exist without its people from top to bottom and maintain the spirit competitiveness for business operation.

In terms of employee engagement it is suggested that managers, supervisors, department heads and team leaders have to protect the interest of the employees by maintaining work culture that is based on the principle of trust and accountability. Regular feedback is very important. During meeting everyone has to be heard, engaged and seek further solutions from their end specially that they are the person who are directly involved. When there are changes and new policy to be imposed, make sure that it is communicated with extra care as this can be intensely personal to employees and can create fear and disagreement. In order to leverage great talents and skills make sure that right people are on the right direction and right position.

Since employee empowerment significantly influences job performance, it is suggested that management continues to endow trust, autonomy and authority to its employees to increase a feeling of pride in their work. Especially that customers are rushed and under pressure, employees deserve to have the sufficient resources and information and power to respond and solve problems in real-time. And in the bigger perspective, it is recommended to instill a culture of empowerment to the entire company but this requires a dedication from every level of leadership.

Furthermore, in order for the employees to enhance its performance at work, it is recommended to set a new and challenging task for them to see if the employee is ready to take another step forward from its current position. Help employees fill skill gaps and increase its value by sponsoring them to workshops, seminars and training. Improve employee's morale by clearly communicating to them how their role can help the company succeed and create an open discussion that talk about areas of concern at their work. To conclude, it is recommended to future researchers to study on the other dimensions and factors that drive, hone and enhance job performance to employees.

REFERENCES

- [1.] Abdollahi, B. Naveh Ebrahim, A (2011). Employees Empowerment. Virayesh publication Tehran.
- [2.] Achtenhagen, L., Melin, L., & Naldi, L. (2013). Dynamics of business models—strategizing, critical capabilities and activities for sustained value creation. *Long range planning*, 46(6), 427-442.
- [3.] Adnan, A. M., Rahman, A. E. A., & Ahmad, R. (2018). Factors Influencing Turnover Intention among Fast Food Restaurant Managers. *Sciences*, 8(17), 195-210.
- [4.] Akinyele, S. T. (2010). The influence of work environment on workers' productivity: A case of selected oil and gas industry in Lagos, Nigeria. *African Journal of Business Management*, 4(3), 299-307.
- [5.] Al Sumaiti, R. S. (2010). The Work Life Balance and Job Satisfaction in Oil and Gas organisations in the UAE context (Doctoral dissertation, The British University in Dubai (BUiD)).
- [6.] Ali, S., & Farooqi, Y. A. (2014). Effect of work overload on job satisfaction, effect of job satisfaction on employee performance and employee engagement (a case of public sector University of Gujranwala Division). *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Sciences and Engineering*, 5(8), 23-30.
- [7.] Ameer, M. H., Bhatti, S., & Baig, S. (2014). Impact of employee empowerment on job satisfaction. *Developing country studies*, 4(9), 114-126.
- [8.] Anitha, J. (2014). Determinants of employee engagement and their impact on employee performance. *International journal of productivity and performance management*.
- [9.] Anthony, McMann, P. E., Ellinger, A. D., Astakhova, M., & Halbesleben, J. R. (2017). Exploring different operationalizations of employee engagement and their relationships with workplace stress and burnout. *Human Resource Development Quarterly*, 28(2), 163-195.
- [10.] Appleton, J. J., Christenson, S. L., & Furlong, M. J. (2008). Student engagement with school: Critical conceptual and methodological issues of the construct. *Psychology in the Schools*, 45(5), 369-386.

- [11.] Arezes, P. M., Dinis-Carvalho, J., & Alves, A. C. (2015). Workplace ergonomics in lean production environments: A literature review. *Work*, 52(1), 57-70.
- [12.] Armache, J. (2013). The Benefits of Employees'Empowerment. *Franklin Business & Law Journal*, 2013(4)
- [13.] Armstrong, M., & Baron, A. (2005). *Managing performance: performance management in action*. CIPD publishing.
- [14.] Augustain, A. N., Agu, O., & Okocha, E. R. (2019). Effect of employee empowerment on the performance of selected manufacturing organisations in Enugu State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Management and Social Sciences*, 8(9), 30-48.
- [15.] Avey, J. B., Luthans, F., & Youssef, C. M. (2010).The additive value of positive psychological capital in predicting work attitudes and behaviors. *Journal of management*, 36(2), 430-452.
- [16.] Awino, Z. B., Ogotu, M., & Musyoka, M. (2018). *Work Culture: Stress Management in Reducing Stress and Improving Organizational Performance*. *China-USA Business Review*, 17(3), 1537-1514.in the Nairobi Securities Exchange.
- [17.] Azar, M., & Shafighi, A. A. (2013). The effect of work motivation on employees' job performance (Case study: employees of Isfahan Islamic Revolution Housing Foundation). *International journal of academic research in business and social sciences*, 3(9), 432.
- [18.] Babatunde, B. O., & Ayodele, M. D. (2018). *Work Environment And Employees' productivity In A Competitive Business Environment*. *Strategii Manageriale*, 56.
- [19.] Bagozzi, R. P. (2011). Measurement and meaning in information systems and organizational research: Methodological and philosophical foundations. *MIS quarterly*, 261-292.
- [20.] Bagozzi, R. P., & Yi, Y. (2012).Specification, evaluation, and interpretation of structural equation models. *Journal of the academy of marketing science*, 40(1), 8-34.
- [21.] Bagyo, Y., 2013. Engagement as a Variable to Improve the Relationship between Leadership, Organizational Culture on the Performance of Employees. *IOSR Journal of Business and Management (IOSR-JBM)*, Vol.14, No.4.
- [22.] Bakker, A. B., & Albrecht, S. (2018). *Work engagement: current trends*. *Career Development International*.
- [23.] Bandura, A. (1986). The explanatory and predictive scope of self-efficacy theory. *Journal of social and clinical psychology*, 4(3), 359-373.
- [24.] Bandura, A. (2000). Cultivate self-efficacy for personal and organizational effectiveness. *Handbook of principles of organization behavior*, 2, 0011-21.
- [25.] Bandura, A. (2010). Self-efficacy. *The Corsini encyclopedia of psychology*, 1-3.
- [26.] Bank, M., & Brustbauer, J. (2014). *Investor sentiment in financial markets*. University of Innsbruck.
- [27.] Baron, A., & Armstrong, M. (2007). *Human capital management: achieving added value through people*. Kogan Page Publishers.
- [28.] Barrales-Molina, V., Martínez-López, F. J., & Gázquez-Abad, J. C. (2014). Dynamic marketing capabilities: Toward an integrative framework. *International Journal of Management Reviews*, 16(4), 397-416.
- [29.] Barrales-Molina, V., Martínez-López, F. J., & Gázquez-Abad, J. C. (2014). Dynamic marketing capabilities: Toward an integrative framework. *International Journal of Management Reviews*, 16(4), 397-416.
- [30.] Basha, S. A., & Maiti, J. (2017). Assessment of work compatibility across employees' demographics: a case study. *International journal of injury control and safety promotion*, 24(1), 106-119.
- [31.] Beattie, V., & Smith, S. J. (2013). Value creation and business models: refocusing the intellectual capital debate. *The British Accounting Review*, 45(4), 243-254.
- [32.] Belas, J., Kljucnikov, A., Vojtovic, S., & Sobeková-Májková, M. (2015).Approach of the SME entrepreneurs to financial risk management in relation to gender and level of education. *Economics & Sociology*, 8(4), 32.
- [33.] Bentler, P. M. (1988). Causal modeling via structural equation systems.In *Handbook of multivariate experimental psychology* (pp. 317-335).Springer, Boston, MA.
- [34.] Berri, D. J., Leeds, M. A., & von Allmen, P. (2015).Salary determination in the presence of fixed revenues. *International Journal of Sport Finance*, 10(1), 5.
- [35.] Bjerke, B., & Hultman, C. (2004). *Entrepreneurial marketing: The growth of small firms in the new economic era*. Edward Elgar Publishing.

- [36.] Block, J., Sandner, P., & Spiegel, F. (2015). How do risk attitudes differ within the group of entrepreneurs? The role of motivation and procedural utility. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 53(1), 183-206.
- [37.] Bordens, K. S., & Abbott, B. B. (2002). *Research design and methods: A process approach*. McGraw-Hill.
- [38.] Bose, I. (2018). Employee Empowerment and Employee Performance: An Empirical Study on Selected Banks in UAE. *Journal of Applied Management and Investments*, 7(2), 71-82.
- [39.] Boussalem, A. B. (2015). Impact of Employees' Empowerment on Sustainable Competitive Advantage. *Revue Chercheur Economique Numéro*.
- [40.] Breevaart, K., Bakker, A., Hetland, J., Demerouti, E., Olsen, O. K., & Espevik, R. (2014). Daily transactional and transformational leadership and daily employee engagement. *Journal of occupational and organizational psychology*, 87(1), 138-157.
- [41.] Bromiley, P., McShane, M., Nair, A., & Rustambekov, E. (2015). Enterprise risk management: Review, critique, and research directions. *Long range planning*, 48(4), 265-276.
- [42.] Brustbauer, J. (2016). Enterprise risk management in SMEs: Towards a structural model. *International Small Business Journal*, 34(1), 70-85.
- [43.] Burgstaller, J., & Wagner, E. (2015). How do family ownership and founder management affect capital structure decisions and adjustment of SMEs? Evidence from a bank-based economy. *The Journal of Risk Finance*, 16(1), 73-101.
- [44.] Byrne, B. M. (2013). *Structural equation modeling with Mplus: Basic concepts, applications, and programming*. routledge.
- [45.] Byrne, Z. S., Peters, J. M., & Weston, J. W. (2016). The struggle with employee engagement: Measures and construct clarification using five samples. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 101(9), 1201.
- [46.] Cascio, W. F., & Luthans, F. (2014). Reflections on the metamorphosis at Robben Island: The role of institutional work and positive psychological capital. *Journal of Management Inquiry*, 23(1), 51-67.
- [47.] Catapano, A. L., Graham, I., De Backer, G., Wiklund, O., Chapman, M. J., Drexel, H., ...& Reiner, Ž. (2016). 2016 ESC/EAS guidelines for the management of dyslipidaemias. *European heart journal*, 37(39), 2999-3058.
- [48.] Celik, A., Cakici, A. B., & Celik, N. (2014). The effects of employee empowerment applications on organizational creativity and innovativeness in enterprises: The case of Oiz. *European Scientific Journal*, 10(10).
- [49.] Centeno, E., Hart, S., & Dinnie, K. (2013). The five phases of SME brand-building. *Journal of Brand Management*, 20(6), 445-457.
- [50.] Chei, C. H., Yee, C. H., Men, L. P., & Bee, L. L. (2014). Factors affecting employees' performance in the hotel industry (Doctoral dissertation, Thesis).
- [51.] Chem, C. A., Hsieh, C. W., & Chen, D. Y. (2014). Fostering public service motivation through workplace trust: Evidence from public managers in Taiwan. *Public Administration*, 92(4), 954-973
- [52.] Chernyak-Hai, L., & Tziner, A. (2016). The "I believe" and the "I invest" of Work-Family Balance: The indirect influences of personal values and work engagement via perceived organizational climate and workplace burnout. *Revista de Psicología del Trabajo y de las Organizaciones*, 32(1), 1-10.
- [53.] Chiang, C. F., & Hsieh, T. S. (2012). The impacts of perceived organizational support and psychological empowerment on job performance: The mediating effects of organizational citizenship behavior. *International journal of hospitality management*, 31(1), 180-190.
- [54.] Chin, W. W. (1998). Commentary: Issues and opinion on structural equation modeling.
- [55.] Christensen, M. (2014). Communication as a strategic tool in change processes. *International journal of business communication*, 51(4), 359-385.
- [56.] Cicolini, G., Comparcini, D., & Simonetti, V. (2014). Workplace empowerment and nurses' job satisfaction: A systematic literature review. *Journal of Nursing Management*, 22(7), 855-871.
- [57.] Cooper, R. G. (2000). Product innovation and technology strategy. *Research-Technology Management*, 43(1), 38-41.
- [58.] Costanza, R., de Groot, R., Sutton, P., Van der Ploeg, S., Anderson, S. J., Kubiszewski, I., ...& Turner, R. K. (2014). Changes in the global value of ecosystem services. *Global environmental change*, 26, 152-158.
- [59.] Crant, J. M. (2000). Proactive behavior in organizations. *Journal of management*, 26(3), 435-462.
- [60.] Crawford, E. R., Rich, B. L., Buckman, B., & Bergeron, J. (2013). The antecedents and drivers of employee engagement. In *Employee engagement in theory and practice* (pp. 71-95). Routledge.

Structural Equation Model of Job Performance among Restaurant Employees in Davao Region

- [61.] Cui, R., Groot, P., Schauer, M., & Heskes, T. (2018). Learning the Causal Structure of Copula Models with Latent Variables. In UAI (pp. 188-197).
- [62.] Cullen, K. L., Edwards, B. D., Casper, W. C., & Gue, K. R. (2014). Employees' adaptability and perceptions of change-related uncertainty: Implications for perceived organizational support, job satisfaction, and performance. *Journal of Business and Psychology*, 29(2), 269-280.
- [63.] De Jong, J. P., & Freel, M. (2010). Absorptive capacity and the reach of collaboration in high technology small firms. *Research policy*, 39(1), 47-54.
- [64.] Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (2014). The importance of universal psychological needs for understanding motivation in the workplace. *The Oxford handbook of work engagement, motivation, and self-determination theory*, 13-32.
- [65.] Degago, E. (2014). A study on impact of psychological empowerment on employee performance in small and medium scale enterprise sectors. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 6(27), 60-72.
- [66.] Demerouti, E., & Bakker, A. B. (2008). The Oldenburg Burnout Inventory: A good alternative to measure burnout and engagement. *Handbook of stress and burnout in health care*, 65-78.
- [67.] Dobre, O. I. (2013). Employee motivation and organizational performance. *Review of applied socio-economic research*, 5(1).
- [68.] Dunning, R., Bloom, J. D., & Creamer, N. (2015). The local food movement, public-private partnerships, and food system resiliency. *Journal of Environmental Studies and Sciences*, 5(4), 661-670.
- [69.] Dust, S. B., Resick, C. J., & Mawritz, M. B. (2014). Transformational leadership, psychological empowerment, and the moderating role of mechanistic-organic contexts. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 35(3), 413-433.
- [70.] Ejerimo, O., & Schubert, T. (2014). Do higher wages reduce inventor's job turnover? The role of utility, status and signaling effects. In DRUID summer conference
- [71.] Ekienabor, E. E. (2016). Impact of job stress on employees' productivity and commitment. *International Journal for Research in Business, Management and Accounting*, 2(5), 124-133.
- [72.] EL-Annan, S. H. (2013). Innovation, proactive, and vision are three integrated dimensions between leadership and entrepreneurship. *European Journal of Business and Social Sciences*, 1(12), 148-163.
- [73.] Elnaga, A. A., & Imran, A. (2014). The impact of employee empowerment on job satisfaction: theoretical study. *American Journal of Research Communication*, 2(1), 13-26.
- [74.] Ensslin, S. R., Ensslin, L., Back, F., & de Oliveira Lacerda, R. T. (2013). Improved decision aiding in human resource management. *International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management*.
- [75.] Falkner, E. M., & Hiebl, M. R. (2015). Risk management in SMEs: a systematic review of available evidence. *The Journal of Risk Finance*, 16(2), 122-144.
- [76.] Farzaneh, J., Dehghanpour Farashah, A., & Kazemi, M. (2014). The impact of person-job fit and person-organization fit on OCB: The mediating and moderating effects of organizational commitment and psychological empowerment. *Personnel Review*, 43(5), 672-691.
- [77.] Fatima, A., Iqbal, M. Z., & Imran, R. (2013). Organizational commitment and counterproductive work behavior: role of employee empowerment. In *Proceedings of the Sixth International Conference on Management Science and Engineering Management* (pp. 665-679). Springer, London.
- [78.] Fatima, Z. (2017). Impact of Compensation Plans on Salesforce Motivation. *Review of Professional Management*, 15(2), 70-76.
- [79.] Feng, H., & Cao, M. (2017). The individual influence factors of voluntary turnover among knowledge workers in China: A case study of Huawei. *Journal of Contemporary Eastern Asia*, 16(2).
- [80.] Ferm, J. (2018). Business model change and internationalization of Finnish cleantech SMEs.
- [81.] Fernandez, S., & Moldogaziev, T. (2013). Employee empowerment, employee attitudes, and performance: Testing a causal model. *Public Administration Review*, 73(3), 490-506.
- [82.] Fernet, C., Trépanier, S. G., Austin, S., Gagné, M., & Forest, J. (2015). Transformational leadership and optimal functioning at work: On the mediating role of employees' perceived job characteristics and motivation. *Work & Stress*, 29(1), 11-31.
- [83.] Fiore, A. M., Niehm, L. S., Hurst, J. L., Son, J., & Sadachar, A. (2013). Entrepreneurial marketing: Scale validation with small, independently-owned businesses. *Journal of Marketing Development and Competitiveness*, 7(4), 63.
- [84.] Fock, H., Hui, M. K., Au, K., & Bond, M. H. (2013). Moderation effects of power distance on the relationship between types of empowerment and employee satisfaction. *Journal of Cross-Cultural Psychology*, 44(2), 281-298.

Structural Equation Model of Job Performance among Restaurant Employees in Davao Region

- [85.] GanjiNia, H., Gilaninia, S., & Sharami, R. P. M. (2013). Overview of Employees Empowerment in Organizations. *Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review (Oman Chapter)*, 3(2), 38.
- [86.] Ganta, V. C. (2014). Motivation in the workplace to improve the employee performance. *International Journal of Engineering Technology, Management and Applied Sciences*, 2(6), 221-230.
- [87.] Gao, S. S., Sung, M. C., & Zhang, J. (2013). Risk management capability building in SMEs: A social capital perspective. *International Small Business Journal*, 31(6), 677-700.
- [88.] Garrett, F. G. (2014). A quantitative analysis of the three-year statute of limitations on appealed tax cases (Doctoral dissertation, Capella University).
- [89.] Gerhart, B., & Fang, M. (2015). Pay, intrinsic motivation, extrinsic motivation, performance, and creativity in the workplace: Revisiting long-held beliefs. *Annu. Rev. Organ. Psychol. Organ. Behav.*, 2(1), 489-521.
- [90.] Goffee, R., & Scase, R. (2015). *The Real World of the Small Business Owner* (Routledge Revivals).Routledge.
- [91.] Gohar, F. R., Bashir, M., Abrar, M., & Asghar, F. (2015).Effect of psychological empowerment, distributive justice and job autonomy on organizational commitment. *International Journal of Information, Business and Management*, 7(1), 144.
- [92.] Gökbulut Özdemir, Ö. (2013). Entrepreneurial marketing and social value creation in Turkish art industry: An ambidextrous perspective. *Journal of Research in Marketing and Entrepreneurship*, 15(1), 39-60.
- [93.] Goncalves, J., Kostakos, V., Karapanos, E., Barreto, M., Camacho, T., Tomasic, A., & Zimmerman, J. (2014). Citizen motivation on the go: the role of psychological empowerment. *Interacting with Computers*, 26(3), 196-207.
- [94.] Gondal, U. H., & Husain, T. (2013). A comparative study of intelligence quotient and emotional intelligence: effect on employees' performance. *Asian journal of Business management*, 5(1), 153-162.
- [95.] Graves, L. M., & Luciano, M. M. (2013). Self-determination at work: Understanding the role of leader-member exchange. *Motivation and Emotion*, 37(3), 518-536.
- [96.] Grinstein, A. (2008). The relationships between market orientation and alternative strategic orientations. *European journal of marketing*.
- [97.] Grönroos, C., & Voima, P. (2013). Critical service logic: making sense of value creation and co-creation. *Journal of the academy of marketing science*, 41(2), 133-150.
- [98.] Guillaume, Y. R., Dawson, J. F., Otake-Ebede, L., Woods, S. A., & West, M. A. (2017). Harnessing demographic differences in organizations: What moderates the effects of workplace diversity?. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 38(2), 276-303.
- [99.] Gummerus, J. (2013). Value creation processes and value outcomes in marketing theory: strangers or siblings?. *Marketing Theory*, 13(1), 19-46.
- [100.] Gupta, S., Swanson, N. J., & Cunningham, D. J. (2010). A study of the effect of age, gender, & gpa on the ethical behavior of accounting students. *Gender, & GPA on the Ethical Behavior of Accounting Students* (August 31, 2010).
- [101.] Hair, J. F., Sarstedt, M., Ringle, C. M., & Mena, J. A. (2012). An assessment of the use of partial least squares structural equation modeling in marketing research. *Journal of the academy of marketing science*, 40(3), 414-433.
- [102.] Hakanen, J. J., Bakker, A. B., & Schaufeli, W. B. (2006). Burnout and work engagement among teachers. *Journal of school psychology*, 43(6), 495-513.
- [103.] Hakanen, J. J., Perhoniemi, R., & Toppinen-Tanner, S. (2008). Positive gain spirals at work: From job resources to work engagement, personal initiative and work-unit innovativeness. *Journal of vocational behavior*, 73(1), 78-91.
- [104.] Hakanen, J. J., Schaufeli, W. B., & Ahola, K. (2008). The Job Demands-Resources model: A three-year cross-lagged study of burnout, depression, commitment, and work engagement. *Work & Stress*, 22(3), 224-241.
- [105.] Halbesleben, J. R., & Wheeler, A. R. (2008).The relative roles of engagement and embeddedness in predicting job performance and intention to leave. *Work & Stress*, 22(3), 242-256.
- [106.] Hallböck, J. and Gabrielsson, P. (2013) 'Entrepreneurial marketing strategies during the growth of international new ventures originating in small and open economies', *International Business Review*, vol. 22, Feb, pp. 1008-1020.
- [107.] Hallback,J. And Gabrielson, P. 2013. Entrepreneurial marketing strategies during the growth of international new ventures originating in small and open economies. *International Business Review*. Pp.1008-1020
- [108.] Hanzae, K., & Mirvansi, M. (2013).A survey on impact of emotional intelligence, organizational citizenship behaviors and job satisfaction on employees' performance in Iranian hotel industry. *Management Science Letters*, 3(5), 1395-1402.

- [109.] Harms, R., Luck, F., Kraus, S., & Walsh, S. (2014). On the motivational drivers of gray entrepreneurship: An exploratory study. *Technological forecasting and social change*, 89, 358-365.
- [110.] Harrison, T., & Waite, K. (2015). Impact of co-production on consumer perception of empowerment. *The Service Industries Journal*, 35(10), 502-520.
- [111.] Hechanova, M. R. M., Alampay, R. B. A., & Franco, E. P. (2006). Psychological empowerment, job satisfaction and performance among Filipino service workers. *Asian journal of social psychology*, 9(1), 72-78.
- [112.] Henseler, J., Hubona, G., & Ray, P. A. (2016). Using PLS path modeling in new technology research: updated guidelines. *Industrial management & data systems*.
- [113.] Hills, G. E., & Hultman, C. (2013). Entrepreneurial marketing: Conceptual and empirical research opportunities. *Entrepreneurship Research Journal*, 3(4), 437-448.
- [114.] Hills, G. E., & LaForge, R. W. (1992). Research at the marketing interface to advance entrepreneurship theory. *Entrepreneurship theory and practice*, 16(3), 33-60.
- [115.] Hitt, M. A., Bierman, L., Shimizu, K., & Kochhar, R. (2001). Direct and moderating effects of human capital on strategy and performance in professional service firms: A resource-based perspective. *Academy of Management journal*, 44(1), 13-28.
- [116.] Holmes, C., & Jorlöv, K. (2015). Entrepreneurial marketing: A descriptive study of Swedish charitable organizations.
- [117.] Hooker, R. R. J. (2015). A two part story: the impact of a culturally responsive working environment on wellbeing; and the job attitudes and factors of retention for indigenous employees: a thesis presented in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the degree of Master of Management in Human Resource Management at Massey University, Turitea campus, Aotearoa-New Zealand (Doctoral dissertation, Massey University).
- [118.] Hoon, B. H. Y., & Parent, D. (2013). Learning and the Form of Compensation. *Journal of Labor Research*, 34(1), 79-98.
- [119.] Ismail, A., & Abd Razak, M. R. (2016). A study on job satisfaction as a determinant of job motivation. *Acta Universitatis Danubius. Economica*, 12(3).
- [120.] Ivancevich, J. M., Konopaske, R., & Matteson, M. T. (2006). *Comportamiento organizacional*. McGraw Hill.
- [121.] Jang, Y. J., Zheng, T., & Bosselman, R. (2017). Top managers' environmental values, leadership, and stakeholder engagement in promoting environmental sustainability in the restaurant industry. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 63, 101-111.
- [122.] Jayaweera, T. (2015). Impact of work environmental factors on job performance, mediating role of work motivation: a study of hotel sector in England. *International journal of business and management*, 10(3), 271.
- [123.] Jha, S. (2014). Transformational leadership and psychological empowerment: Determinants of organizational citizenship behavior. *South Asian Journal of Global Business Research*, 3(1), 18-35.
- [124.] Jogaratnam, G. (2002). Entrepreneurial orientation and environmental hostility: an assessment of small, independent restaurant businesses. *Journal of Hospitality & Tourism Research*, 26(3), 258-277.
- [125.] Jogaratnam, G. (2017). How organizational culture influences market orientation and business performance in the restaurant industry. *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Management*, 31, 211-219.
- [126.] Jones, J. R., Ni, J., & Wilson, D. C. (2009). Comparative effects of race/ethnicity and employee engagement on withdrawal behavior. *Journal of managerial issues*, 21(2), 195.
- [127.] Joo, B. K., & Lim, T. (2013). Transformational leadership and career satisfaction: The mediating role of psychological empowerment. *Journal of Leadership & Organizational Studies*, 20(3), 316-326.
- [128.] Jose, G., & Mampilly, S. R. (2014). Psychological empowerment as a predictor of employee engagement: An empirical attestation. *Global Business Review*, 15(1), 93-104.
- [129.] Kahreh, M. S., Ahmadi, H., & Hashemi, (2011). Achieving competitive advantage through empowering employees: An empirical study. *Far East Journal of Psychology and Business*, 3(2), 26-37.
- [130.] Kahya, E. (2007). The effects of job characteristics and working conditions on job performance. *International journal of industrial ergonomics*, 37(6), 515-523.
- [131.] Karatepe, O. M. (2013). High-performance work practices and hotel employee performance: The mediation of work engagement. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 32, 132-140.
- [132.] Karatepe, O. M. (2013). High-performance work practices and hotel employee performance: The mediation of work engagement. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 32, 132-140.

- [133.] Karatepe, O. M., & Karadas, G. (2015). Do psychological capital and work engagement foster frontline employees' satisfaction? A study in the hotel industry. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 27(6), 1254-1278.
- [134.] Karatepe, O. M., & Kilic, H. (2015). Does manager support reduce the effect of work-family conflict on emotional exhaustion and turnover intentions?. *Journal of Human Resources in Hospitality & Tourism*, 14(3), 267-289.
- [135.] Karatepe, O. M., & Talebzadeh, N. (2016). An empirical investigation of psychological capital among flight attendants. *Journal of Air Transport Management*, 55, 193-202.
- [136.] Karavardar, G. (2014). Perceived organizational support, psychological empowerment, organizational citizenship behavior, job performance and job embeddedness: A research on the fast food industry in Istanbul, Turkey. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 9(4), 131.
- [137.] Kaya, Ö. (2015). Design of work place and ergonomics in garment enterprises. *Procedia Manufacturing*, 3, 6437-6443.
- [138.] Keenoy, T. (2013). *Engagement: A murmuration of objects*. London: Routledge.
- [139.] Kim, B. P., Losekoot, E., & Milne, S. (2013). Consequences of empowerment among restaurant servers. *Management Decision*.
- [140.] Kimolo, K. I. M. A. N. Z. I. (2013). The relationship between employee empowerment practices and employee performance in regional development authorities in Kenya. Degree of Masters of Business Administration (MBA). School of Business Administration. University of Nairobi.
- [141.] Kirsch, C. (2016). What is 'Employee Engagement'? - Analysis of the Factor Structure of the Engagement Construct.
- [142.] Kowalkowski, C., Witell, L., & Gustafsson, A. (2013). Any way goes: Identifying value constellations for service infusion in SMEs. *Industrial Marketing Management*, 42(1), 18-30.
- [143.] Kraiczy, N. D., Hack, A., & Kellermanns, F. W. (2015). What makes a family firm innovative? CEO risk-taking propensity and the organizational context of family firms. *Journal of Product Innovation Management*, 32(3), 334-348.
- [144.] Kuratko, D. F., & Audretsch, D. B. (2013). Clarifying the domains of corporate entrepreneurship. *International Entrepreneurship and Management Journal*, 9(3), 323-335.
- [145.] Lamore, P. R., Berkowitz, D., & Farrington, P. A. (2013). Proactive/responsive market orientation and marketing - research and development integration. *Journal of Product Innovation Management*, 30(4), 695-711.
- [146.] Lavia López, O., & Hiebl, M. R. (2014). Management accounting in small and medium-sized enterprises: current knowledge and avenues for further research. *Journal of Management Accounting Research*, 27(1), 81-119.
- [147.] Lazar, I., Osoian, C., & Ratiu, P. (2010). The role of work-life balance practices in order to improve organizational performance. *European Research Studies*, 13(1), 201.
- [148.] Lee, M., & Koh, J. (2001). Is empowerment really a new concept?. *International journal of human resource management*, 12(4), 684-695.
- [149.] Lee, S., Singal, M., & Kang, K. H. (2013). The corporate social responsibility-financial performance link in the US restaurant industry: do economic conditions matter?. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 32, 2-10.
- [150.] Lee, Y. K., Kim, S. H., Seo, M. K., & Hight, S. K. (2015). Market orientation and business performance: Evidence from franchising industry. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 44, 28-37.
- [151.] Lefcourt, H. M. (Ed.). (2014). *Locus of control: Current trends in theory & research*. Psychology Press.
- [152.] Lennick, D., & Kiel, F. (2011). *Moral Intelligence 2.0: Enhancing Business Performance and Leadership Success in Turbulent Times*, Portable Documents. Pearson Prentice Hall.
- [153.] Lin, L. F., & Tseng, C. C. (2013). The influence of leadership behavior and psychological empowerment on job satisfaction. *International Journal of Organizational Innovation (Online)*, 5(4), 21.
- [154.] Lioyd L. Byars and Leslie W. Rue, (2000), *Human Resource Management 6 th edition*
- [155.] Long, H. C. (2013). The relationship among learning orientation, market orientation, entrepreneurial orientation, and firm performance of Vietnam marketing communications firms. *Philippine Management Review*, 20.
- [156.] Lorinkova, N. M., Pearsall, M. J., & Sims Jr, H. P. (2013). Examining the differential longitudinal performance of directive versus empowering leadership in teams. *Academy of Management Journal*, 56(2), 573-596.
- [157.] Lumpkin, G. T., & Dess, G. G. (2001). Linking two dimensions of entrepreneurial orientation to firm performance: The moderating role of environment and industry life cycle. *Journal of business venturing*, 16(5), 429-451.

- [158.] Lumpkin, G. T., & Dess, G. G. (2001). Linking two dimensions of entrepreneurial orientation to firm performance: The moderating role of environment and industry life cycle. *Journal of business venturing*, 16(5), 429-451.
- [159.] Luoh, H. F., Tsaor, S. H., & Tang, Y. Y. (2014). Empowering employees: job standardization and innovative behavior. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*.
- [160.] MacEachen, E., Polzer, J., & Clarke, J. (2008). "You are free to set your own hours": Governing worker productivity and health through flexibility and resilience. *Social Science & Medicine*, 66(5), 1019-1033.
- [161.] Mach, M., & Baruch, Y. (2015). Team performance in cross cultural project teams: The moderated mediation role of consensus, heterogeneity, faultlines and trust. *Cross Cultural Management*, 22(3), 464-486.
- [162.] Mahr, D., Lievens, A., & Blazevic, V. (2014). The value of customer cocreated knowledge during the innovation process. *Journal of Product Innovation Management*, 31(3), 599-615.
- [163.] Malik, F., Chughtai, S., Iqbal, Z., & Ramzan, M. (2013). Does psychological empowerment bring about employee commitment? evidence from telecommunication sector of Pakistan. *Journal of Business Studies Quarterly*, 5(1), 14.
- [164.] Mani, V. (2011). Analysis of employee engagement and its predictors. *International Journal of Human Resource Studies*, 1(2), 15.
- [165.] Marcelino-Sádaba, S., Pérez-Ezcurdia, A., Lazcano, A. M. E., & Villanueva, P. (2014). Project risk management methodology for small firms. *International journal of project management*, 32(2), 327-340.
- [166.] Martela, F., & Riekk, T. J. (2018). Autonomy, competence, relatedness, and beneficence: a multicultural comparison of the four pathways to meaningful work. *Frontiers in psychology*, 9, 1157.
- [167.] McCann, J. T., Sparks, B. H., & Kohntopp, T. F. (2017). Leadership Integrity and Diversity in the Workplace. *Research in Economics and Management*, 2(5), 177.
- [168.] Mehrabani, S. E., & Shajari, M. (2013). Relationship between employee empowerment and employee effectiveness. *Service science and management research*, 2(4), 60-68.
- [169.] Men, L. R., & Stacks, D. W. (2013). The impact of leadership style and employee empowerment on perceived organizational reputation. *Journal of Communication Management*, 17(2), 171-192
- [170.] Mengting, X., & Zhang, X. (2015). Value creation through entrepreneurial marketing: A qualitative case study for Swedish milk industry.
- [171.] Menguc, B., Auh, S., Fisher, M., & Haddad, A. (2013). To be engaged or not to be engaged: The antecedents and consequences of service employee engagement. *Journal of Business Research*, 66(11), 2163-2170.
- [172.] Meyerson, G., & Dewettinck, B. (2012). Effect of empowerment on employees performance. *Advanced Research in Economic and Management Sciences*, 2(1), 40-46.
- [173.] Mishra, K., Boynton, L., & Mishra, A. (2014). Driving employee engagement: The expanded role of internal communications. *International Journal of Business Communication*, 51(2), 183-202.
- [174.] Mone, E. M., & London, M. (2014). Employee engagement through effective performance management: A practical guide for managers. Routledge.
- [175.] Mortimer, D. (2010). Employee engagement: 5 Factors that matter to employees. Retrieved from.
- [176.] Mostert, F. F., Nell, K., Mostert, K., & Rothmann, S. (2008). Outcomes of occupational stress in a higher education institution. *Southern African Business Review*, 12(3), 102-127.
- [177.] Mullins, L. J. (2007). Management and organisational behaviour. Pearson education.
- [178.] Munir, K. (2011). Impact of stressors on the performance of employees.
- [179.] Munisamy, S. (2013). Identifying factors that influence job performance amongst employees in oil palm plantation-FASS Final Project (Psychology).
- [180.] Naharuddin, N., & Sadegi, M. (2013). Factors of workplace environment that affect employees performance: A case study of Miyazu Malaysia.
- [181.] Namasivayam, K., Guchait, P., & Lei, P. (2014). The influence of leader empowering behaviors and employee psychological empowerment on customer satisfaction. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 26(1), 69-84.
- [182.] Nazem, F., Mozaiini, M., & Seifi, A. (2014). The Structural Model of Performance Based on the Empowerment of University Staff.

- [183.] Njoroge, R. W. (2018). The Influence Of Employee Empowerment On Employee Commitment Among Academic Staff At Jomo Kenyatta University Of Agriculture AND TECHNOLOGY (JKUAT) (Doctoral dissertation, UNIVERSITY OF NAIROBI).
- [184.] Nuryakin, N., Aryanto, V. D. W., & Setiawan, M. B. (2018). Mediating effect of value creation in the relationship between relational capabilities on business performance. *Contaduría y administración*, 63(1), 9.
- [185.] Nwaizugbu, I. C. & Anukam, A. I. (2014). Assessment of Entrepreneurial Marketing Among Small and Medium Enterprises in Imo State Nigeria: Prospects and Challenges (pdf).
- [186.] Obicci, P. A. (2015). Effects of ethical leadership on employee performance in Uganda. *Net journal of business management*, 3(1), 1-12.
- [187.] O'Casey, A., & Sok, P. (2013). Exploring innovation driven value creation in B2B service firms: The roles of the manager, employees, and customers in value creation. *Journal of Business Research*, 66(8), 1074-1084.
- [188.] Olafsen, A. H., Halvari, H., Forest, J., & Deci, E. L. (2015). Show them the money? The role of pay, managerial need support, and justice in a self-determination theory model of intrinsic work motivation. *Scandinavian journal of psychology*, 56(4), 447-457.
- [189.] Oplatka, I. (2017). 'I'm So Tired and Have No Time for My Family!': The Consequences of Heavy Workload in Principals'hip. *International Studies in Educational Administration (Commonwealth Council for Educational Administration & Management (CCEAM))*, 45(2).
- [190.] Orletsky, D. W. (2015). The Use of Proportional Reasoning and Rational Number Concepts by Adults in the Workplace. Arizona State University.
- [191.] Özdemir, Ö. G. (2013). Entrepreneurial marketing and social value creation in Turkish art industry: An ambidextrous perspective. *Journal of Research in Marketing and Entrepreneurship*, 15(1), 39-60.
- [192.] Pels, J., Polese, F., & Brodie, R. J. (2012). Value co-creation: using a viable systems approach to draw implications from organizational theories. *Mercati e Competitività*.
- [193.] Pfeifer, C. (2014). Base salaries, bonus payments, and work absence among managers in a German company. *Scottish Journal of Political Economy*, 61(5), 523-536.
- [194.] Portoghese, I., Galletta, M., Coppola, R. C., Finco, G., & Campagna, M. (2014). Burnout and workload among health care workers: the moderating role of job control. *Safety and health at work*, 5(3), 152-157.
- [195.] Prins, J. T., Van Der Heijden, F. M. M. A., Hoekstra-Weebers, J. E. H. M., Bakker, A. B., Van de Wiel, H. B. M., Jacobs, B., & Gazendam-Donofrio, S. M. (2009). Burnout, engagement and resident physicians' self-reported errors. *Psychology, health & medicine*, 14(6), 654-666.
- [196.] Qian, X., Shi, Y., & Zhou, H. (2015). Chinese New Generation Employees' Turnover Intentions: Effects of Person-Organization Fit, Core Self-evaluations and Perceived Opportunities. In *Proceedings of the Ninth International Conference on Management Science and Engineering Management* (pp. 1077-1085). Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg.
- [197.] Qureshi, M. I., Iftikhar, M., Abbas, S. G., Hassan, U., Khan, K., & Zaman, K. (2013). Relationship between job stress, workload, environment and employees turnover intentions: What we know, what should we know. *World Applied Sciences Journal*, 23(6), 764-770.
- [198.] Qureshi, M. I., Iftikhar, M., Abbas, S. G., Hassan, U., Khan, K., & Zaman, K. (2013). Relationship between job stress, workload, environment and employees turnover intentions: What we know, what should we know. *World Applied Sciences Journal*, 23(6), 764-770.
- [199.] Rasouli, N., Montazeri, M., Nekouei, M. H., & Zahedi, H. (2013). Investigating the relationship between spiritual leadership and employees psychological empowerment in khozestan utility. *International Business Management*, 7(2), 55-64.
- [200.] Raub, S., & Robert, C. (2013). Empowerment, organizational commitment, and voice behavior in the hospitality industry: Evidence from a multinational sample. *Cornell Hospitality Quarterly*, 54(2), 136-148.
- [201.] Razak, N. A., Ma'amor, H., & Hassan, N. (2016). Measuring reliability and validity instruments of work environment towards quality work life. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 37, 520-528.
- [202.] Raziq, A., & Maulabakhsh, R. (2015). Impact of working environment on job satisfaction. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 23, 717-725.
- [203.] Rengiah, P., & Sentosa, I. (2014). A Structural Equation Modelling of Entrepreneurial Education and Entrepreneurial Intentions among Malaysian University Students. *International Journal of Business and Management Invention*, 3(11), 20-25.
- [204.] Rezaie, D. H., Saleh, P. A., Iman, A. M., & Jaafar, A. (2012). An analysis of the empowerment level of employees and its relation to organizational factors. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 3(15).

- [205.] Robbins, T. L., Crino, M. D., & Fredendall, L. D. (2002). An integrative model of the empowerment process. *Human resource management review*, 12(3), 419-443.
- [206.] Robinson, L., Stamps, M. B., Marshall, G. W., & Lamb, C. W. (2015). Employee Satisfaction and Internal Service Performance: Some Preliminary Evidence. In *Proceedings of the 1999 Academy of Marketing Science (AMS) Annual Conference* (pp. 347-353). Springer, Cham.
- [207.] Rodell, J. B. (2013). Finding meaning through volunteering: Why do employees volunteer and what does it mean for their jobs?. *Academy of Management Journal*, 56(5), 1274-1294.
- [208.] Rosso, B. D., Dekas, K. H., & Wrzesniewski, A. (2010). On the meaning of work: A theoretical integration and review. *Research in organizational behavior*, 30, 91-127.
- [209.] Rutland, P., (1994), —Successful leadership morphologies for 21st century projects . *Proceedings of the INTERNET 12th World Congress on Project Management, Oslo, June Vol. 1*, pp. 552-566
- [210.] Ryan, R. M., & Deci, E. L. (2013). Toward a Social Psychology of Assimilation: Self-Determination Theory in Cognitive. Self-regulation and autonomy: Social and developmental dimensions of human conduct, 40, 191.
- [211.] Saif, N. I., & Saleh, A. S. (2013). Psychological empowerment and job satisfaction in Jordanian hospitals. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 3(16), 250-257.
- [212.] Saks, A. M. (2006). Antecedents and consequences of employee engagement. *Journal of managerial psychology*.
- [213.] Saks, A. M., & Gruman, J. A. (2014). What do we really know about employee engagement?. *Human Resource Development Quarterly*, 25(2), 155-182.
- [214.] Salanova, M., Agut, S., & Peiró, J. M. (2005). Linking organizational resources and work engagement to employee performance and customer loyalty: the mediation of service climate. *Journal of applied Psychology*, 90(6), 1217.
- [215.] Salunke, G. (2015). Work Environment and its effect on job satisfaction in cooperative sugar factories in Maharashtra, India. *Abhinav International Monthly Refereed Journal of Research in Management & Technology*, 4(5), 21-31.
- [216.] Saradha, H., & Patrick, H. A. (2011). Employee engagement in relation to organizational citizenship behavior in information technology organizations. *Journal of Marketing and Management*, 2(2), 74-90.
- [217.] Schaufeli, W. B. (2013). What is engagement?. In *Employee engagement in theory and practice* (pp. 29-49). Routledge.
- [218.] Schaufeli, W. B., & Bakker, A. B. (2004). Job demands, job resources, and their relationship with burnout and engagement: A multi-sample study. *Journal of Organizational Behavior: The International Journal of Industrial, Occupational and Organizational Psychology and Behavior*, 25(3), 293-315.
- [219.] Schaufeli, W. B., Bakker, A. B., & Van Rhenen, W. (2009). How changes in job demands and resources predict burnout, work engagement, and sickness absenteeism. *Journal of Organizational Behavior: The International Journal of Industrial, Occupational and Organizational Psychology and Behavior*, 30(7), 893-917.
- [220.] Schaufeli, W., & Salanova, M. A. R. I. S. (2014). Burnout, boredom and engagement at the workplace.
- [221.] Schutte, N. S., & Loi, N. M. (2014). Connections between emotional intelligence and workplace flourishing. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 66, 134-139.
- [222.] Semmer, N. K. (2007). Recognition and Respect (or lack thereof) as predictors of occupational health and well-being. Paper presentation at World Health Organization, Geneva.
- [223.] Shanmugam, V., & Marsh, J. (2015). Application of Structural Equation Modeling to the Social Sciences: A Brief Guide for Researchers. *Mesure et évaluation en éducation*, 37(3), 99-123.
- [224.] Sharma, P. N., & Kirkman, B. L. (2015). Leveraging leaders: A literature review and future lines of inquiry for empowering leadership research. *Group & Organization Management*, 40(2), 193-237.
- [225.] Sheth, J. N., Sisodia, R. S., & Sharma, A. (2000). The antecedents and consequences of customer-centric marketing. *Journal of the Academy of marketing Science*, 28(1), 55-66.
- [226.] Shuck, B., & Reio Jr, T. G. (2014). Employee engagement and well-being: A moderation model and implications for practice. *Journal of Leadership & Organizational Studies*, 21(1), 43-58.
- [227.] Shuck, B., Ghosh, R., Zigarmi, D., & Nimon, K. (2013). The jingle jangle of employee engagement: Further exploration of the emerging construct and implications for workplace learning and performance. *Human Resource Development Review*, 12(1), 11-35.
- [228.] Silvet, J. (2013). Learned helplessness during organisational change. *Annals of the Alexandru Ioan Cuza University-Economics*, 60(2), 93-103.

- [229.] Simón-Moya, V., Revuelto-Taboada, L., & Guerrero, R. F. (2014). Institutional and economic drivers of entrepreneurship: An international perspective. *Journal of Business Research*, 67(5), 715-721.
- [230.] Singh, M. P., Chakraborty, A., & Roy, M. (2016). Entrepreneurial commitment, organizational sustainability and business performance of manufacturing MSMEs: Evidence from India. *Int. J. Appl. Bus. Econ. Res.*, 14(6), 4615-4631.
- [231.] Smit, Y., & Watkins, J. A. (2012). A literature review of small and medium enterprises (SME) risk management practices in South Africa. *African journal of business management*, 6(21), 6324.
- [232.] Sohail, M., & Rehman, C. A. (2015). Stress and health at the workplace-a review of the literature. *Journal of Business Studies Quarterly*, 6(3), 94.
- [233.] Soltani, I., & Sanatzadeh, S. (2013). Analysis of effective factors on psychological empowerment of employees. *International Journal of Management Academy*, 1(2), 102-108.
- [234.] Sørensen, F., & Jensen, J. F. (2015). Value creation and knowledge development in tourism experience encounters. *Tourism Management*, 46, 336-346.
- [235.] Spector, P. E. (1997). *Job satisfaction: Application, assessment, causes, and consequences* (Vol. 3). Sage publications.
- [236.] Spreitzer, G. M. (1996). Social structural characteristics of psychological empowerment. *Academy of management journal*, 39(2), 483-504.
- [237.] Stenholm, P., Pukkinen, T., & Heinonen, J. (2016). Firm growth in family businesses – The role of entrepreneurial orientation and the entrepreneurial activity. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 54(2), 697-713.
- [238.] Straub, D., Boudreau, M. C., & Gefen, D. (2004). Validation guidelines for IS positivist research. *Communications of the Association for Information systems*, 13(1), 24.
- [239.] Strom, D. L., Sears, K. L., & Kelly, K. M.
- [240.] (2014). Work engagement: The roles of organizational justice and leadership style in predicting engagement among employees. *Journal of Leadership & Organizational Studies*, 21(1), 71-82.
- [241.] Su, S., Li, J., Huang, Q., Huang, X., Shuang, K., & Wang, J. (2013). Cost-efficient task scheduling for executing large programs in the cloud. *Parallel Computing*, 39(4-5), 177-188.
- [242.] Suarathana, J. H. P., & Riana, I. G. (2016). The effect of psychological contract breach and workload on intention to leave: mediating role of job stress. *Procedia-Social and behavioral sciences*, 219, 717-723.
- [243.] Subramony, M. (2009). A meta-analytic investigation of the relationship between HRM bundles and firm performance. *Human resource management*, 48(5), 745-768.
- [244.] Suchart, T. (2017). Factors Influencing Opportunity Driven Nascent Entrepreneurs in Europe and Asia. *European Research Studies*, 20(3A), 774.
- [245.] Suharno, P., & Despinur, D. (2017). The impact of work motivation and competence on employee performance through service quality in administrative staff of Universitas Negeri Jakarta, Indonesia. *Russian Journal of Agricultural and Socio-Economic Sciences*, 61(1).
- [246.] Sundaray, B. K. (2011). Employee engagement: A driver of organizational effectiveness. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 3(8), 53-59.
- [247.] Supaman, L., Nasir, M., & Serif, S. (2019). The Effect of Leadership on Working Conditions, Work Motivation, and Organization Commitment. *Global Journal of Management And Business Research*.
- [248.] Tantalo, C., & Priem, R. L. (2016). Value creation through stakeholder synergy. *Strategic Management Journal*, 37(2), 314-329.
- [249.] Tescari, F. C., & Brito, L. A. L. (2016). Value creation and capture in buyer-supplier relationships: A new perspective. *Revista de Administração de Empresas*, 56(5), 474-488.
- [250.] Toghræe, M. T., Rezvani, M., Mobaraki, M. H., & Farsi, J. Y. (2017). A systematic review on entrepreneurial marketing: three decade research on entrepreneurial marketing. *International Journal of Applied Business and Economic Research*, 15(8), 273-296.
- [251.] Truss, C., Shantz, A., Soane, E., Alfes, K., & Delbridge, R. (2013). Employee engagement, organisational performance and individual well-being: exploring the evidence, developing the theory.
- [252.] Tubbs, S. L., & Moss, S. L. (2000). *Human communication*. TURANLIGİL, F. G., & ALTINTAŞ, V. (2018). ANALYSIS OF INDUSTRY PERCEPTIONS AND EXPECTATIONS OF TOURISM STUDENTS: A CASE STUDY IN TURKEY. *GeoJournal of Tourism & Geosites*, 21(1).

- [253.] Ugboro, I. O. (2006). Organizational commitment, job redesign, employee empowerment and intent to quit among survivors of restructuring and downsizing. *Journal of Behavioral & Applied Management*, 7(3).
- [254.] Ukandu, N. E., & Ukpere, W. I. (2013). Effects of Poor Training and Development on the Work Performance of the Fast Food Employees in Cape Town. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 4(14), 571.
- [255.] Ukandu, N. E., & Ukpere, W. I. (2014). Factors impacting job satisfaction of employees in the fast food industry in Cape Town. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 5(3), 51.
- [256.] Umeze, G. E., & Ohen, S. B. (2015). Marketing Mix Strategies and Entrepreneurial Competence: Evidence from Micro Restaurants in Calabar Metropolis, Cross River State, Nigeria (No. 1008-2016-80313).
- [257.] Valliere, D. (2013). Towards a schematic theory of entrepreneurial alertness. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 28(3), 430-442.
- [258.] Van Wingerden, J., Derks, D., & Bakker, A. B. (2017). The impact of personal resources and job crafting interventions on work engagement and performance. *Human Resource Management*, 56(1), 51-67.
- [259.] Verbano, C., & Venturini, K. (2013). Managing risks in SMEs: A literature review and research agenda. *Journal of technology management & innovation*, 8(3), 186-197.
- [260.] Vermeer, T. (2016). The relationship between business models and firm performance as measured through business model components (Bachelor's thesis, University of Twente).
- [261.] Viljakainen, A., & Toivonen, M. (2014). The futures of magazine publishing: Servitization and co-creation of customer value. *Futures*, 64, 19-28.
- [262.] Wagner, S. M., Eggert, A., & Lindemann, E. (2010). Creating and appropriating value in collaborative relationships. *Journal of business research*, 63(8), 840-848.
- Judge, T. A., Jackson, C. L., Shaw, J. C., Scott, B. A., & Rich, B. L. (2007). Self-efficacy and work-related performance: The integral role of individual differences. *Journal of applied psychology*, 92(1), 107.
- [263.] Walker, A. (2015). Project management in construction. John Wiley & Sons.
- [264.] Wang, G., & Lee, P. D. (2009). Psychological empowerment and job satisfaction: An analysis of interactive effects. *Group & Organization Management*, 34(3), 271-296.
- [265.] Wang, J. L., Zhang, D. J., & Jackson, L. A. (2013). Influence of self-esteem, locus of control, and organizational climate on psychological empowerment in a sample of Chinese teachers. *Journal of Applied Social Psychology*, 43(7), 1428-1435.
- [266.] Wang, Y. L., Ellinger, A. D., & Jim Wu, Y. C. (2013). Entrepreneurial opportunity recognition: an empirical study of R&D personnel. *Management Decision*, 51(2), 248-266.
- [267.] Williams, C. C., & Youssef, Y. (2014). Is informal sector entrepreneurship necessity-or opportunity-driven? Some lessons from urban Brazil. *Business and Management Research*, 3(1), 41.
- [268.] Wong Humborstad, S., GL Nerstad, C., & Dysvik, A. (2014). Empowering leadership, employee goal orientations and work performance: A competing hypothesis approach. *Personnel Review*, 43(2), 246-271.
- [269.] Xanthopoulou, D., Bakker, A. B., Demerouti, E., & Schaufeli, W. B. (2009). Work engagement and financial returns: A diary study on the role of job and personal resources. *Journal of occupational and organizational psychology*, 82(1), 183-200.
- [270.] Yang, L., & Wang, D. (2014). The impacts of top management team characteristics on entrepreneurial strategic orientation: the moderating effects of industrial environment and corporate ownership. *Management Decision*, 52(2), 378-409.
- [271.] Yilmaz, A. K., Ali, I., & Flouris, T. (2015). The effect of corporate social responsibility on pride in membership, job satisfaction and employee engagement. *Journal of Economics, Management and Trade*, 1-12.
- [272.] York, J. G., & Venkataraman, S. (2010). The entrepreneur-environment nexus: Uncertainty, innovation, and allocation. *Journal of business Venturing*, 25(5), 449-463.
- [273.] Zablah, A. R., Carlson, B. D., Donovan, D. T., Maxham III, J. G., & Brown, T. J. (2016). A cross-lagged test of the association between customer satisfaction and employee job satisfaction in a relational context. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 101(5), 743.
- [274.] Zall, M.R., Faghih, N., Ghotbi, S., Sahar, R. (2013). The Effect of Necessity and Opportunity Driven Entrepreneurship on Business Growth
- [275.] Zameer, H., Ali, S., Nisar, W., & Amir, M. (2014). The impact of the motivation on the employee's performance in beverage industry of Pakistan. *International journal of academic research in accounting, finance and management sciences*, 4(1), 293-298.
- [276.] Zeriti, A., Robson, M. J., Spyropoulou, S., & Leonidou, C. N. (2014). Sustainable export marketing strategy fit and performance. *Journal of International Marketing*, 22(4), 44-66.